

Report for Schmidt Ocean Institute's RV *Falkor (too)* + ROV *SuBastian*

Expedition Fkt231202

Octopus Odyssey (too) - Part 2

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Dates: 1 December 2023 to 15 December 2023;

Ports: Balboa, Panama to Golfito, Costa Rica

Mobilization: 30 November 2023, Demobilization: 16 December 2023

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Summary

Cruise objectives and importance of doing this work:

Seamount ecosystems support highly diverse animal communities on the seafloor and the surrounding ocean, yet the diversity, connectivity and ecosystem services of these environments is poorly understood. This knowledge gap confounds efforts to delineate areas in need of conservation management and protection. The Pacific Ocean margin of Costa Rica contains a range of seamount habitats, from the rough terrain of the southwestern margin to the more sparse terrain of the northwest margin. While the southwestern terrain has previously been surveyed (including by *RV Falkor* classic) and some seamount areas here are already protected, far less is known about the ecosystems of the northwestern terrain. In 2013/2014 very unique animal behaviors and hydrothermal venting were discovered with ROV Jason and HOV Alvin on a small feature in the northwestern terrain. Namely, extensive aggregations of octopus were observed at a place called the Dorado Outcrop, located in areas of diffuse venting of slightly warmed hydrothermal fluids. At the time of discovery, it was unclear if these aggregations could be considered nurseries, since no viable eggs were observed with brooding mothers. Subsequently, similar behaviors were observed on the Davidson Seamount offshore California, and those aggregations were confirmed to be octopus nurseries.

In June of 2023, an international team traveled to this region aboard *RV Falkor (too)* for the Octopus Odyssey expedition with a major goal to determine if the eggs at the nursery were viable, as past expeditions to the outcrop had never seen evidence of developing embryos. On their first ROV dive at the nursery in June, the team witnessed baby octopus hatching. They also found the fifth known octopus nursery in the world on a different seafloor feature 30 nautical miles away. The team also explored four other seafloor features on Octopus Odyssey, revealing an incredibly rich biodiversity and biogeography of ancient volcanoes offshore Costa Rica. The team also documented additional evidence of the hydrogeology of the region – how water moves in, out, and through oceanic crust. Such data can inform why volcanoes and earthquakes in Costa Rica vary as different types of seamounts and oceanic crust subducts beneath overriding plates.

As the final shakedown expedition of *RV Falkor (too)* in 2023, the Octopus Odyssey (too) team returned to this region to ask new questions about the connection of life, rocks, and fluids around these seafloor features. Are the octopus nurseries active at a different time of year? Do octopus brooding in hydrothermal springs have different microbiomes as compared to other octopus, and are those microbiomes connected to the microbes in the hydrothermal springs or surrounding rocks? Are the hydrothermal spring fluids from different sites unique, representing different trends in fluid-rock-life reactions, or do they represent a single altered fluid? Are there seasonal trends in biodiversity on the seafloor or in the water above? Sensors and experiments deployed by the team in June would be recovered on the December expedition to help address these questions, aided by interfacing new technology onto the ROV SuBastian.

Equally as important to the science objectives, continuing the theme of capacity sharing, early career development, and raising awareness of deep-sea heritage in Latin American were major objectives of the expedition. The international Octopus Odyssey (too) team gathered anew for collaborative co-production of knowledge and training with Costa Ricans, honoring the work in Costa Rica's waters. Spanish-speaking scientists were given priority for dive lead watches to enable live-stream narration in Spanish, and priority for leadership experience. Ship-to-shore engagements were also prioritized for Spanish-speaking audiences, particularly in Costa Rica. These efforts were intended to raise the profile of deep-sea heritage in Costa Rica ahead of the 2024 UN Ocean Conference meeting happening in Costa Rica in June 2024.

Geographical area

Figure 1. Seafloor features within the proposed Pampa Submarina region of the Pacific Ocean offshore Costa Rica.

The Fkt231202 Octopus Odyssey (too) expedition was the final 2023 shakedown expedition of the RV *Falkor* (too). The expedition targeted an area of ancient volcanoes offshore Costa Rica (Figure 1). Six of these features were explored on the Octopus Odyssey expedition in 2023; this second expedition planned to return to these features.

As part of the work of this expedition, and using multibeam bathymetric data collected on these expeditions combined with prior datasets, the team submitted a proposal to the Costa Rican Commission for Nomenclature on 14 December 2023 to propose official names for these features and the region. If the commission agrees, they will forward these names to GEBCO. The table below lists these proposed names (Table 1).

Table 1. List of the seafloor features in the “Pampa Submarina” region.

Proposed Name	Designation used on Fkt230602 or in prior publications	Bathymetric features
El Dorado Hill	Dorado Outcrop	Elongated (1.7 x 0.4 km), height 115m, base 3080 mbsl, summit 2965m
Tengosed Seamount	Tengosed Seamount	Round (10km diameter), height 1200m, base 3100 mbsl, summit 1900 mbsl
Fuente Knoll	Fuente	Round (5 km diameter), height 550m, base 3100 mbsl, summit 2550 mbsl
Mambo Kita Hill	Unnamed outcrop SW of Fuente	Elongated (6 x 2.5 km), height 140m, base 3150 mbsl, summit 3010 mbsl
Caballito Knoll	Caballito	Round (4-6 km diameter), height 360m, base 3150 mbsl, summit 2790 mbsl
La Pulpería	Unnamed outcrop East of Caballito	Elongated (12 x 7 km), height 270m, base 3120 mbsl, summit 2859 mbsl
Rosquilla Knoll	A	Round (7 km diameter), height 640m, base 3100 mbsl, summit 2460 mbsl
Natu Knoll	Buquito	Round (8 km diameter), height 900m, base 3000 mbsl, summit 2100 mbsl
Nituri Hill	C	Elongated (10 x 5 km), height 500m, base 3100 mbsl, summit 2600 mbsl
Xolotl Hills	B	West: Round (4 km diameter), height 400m, base 3060 mbsl, summit 2660 mbsl East: Round (4 km diameter), height 300m, base 3060 mbsl, summit 2760 mbsl
Kapo Hill	La Misma	Round (5 km diameter), height 315m, base 3700 mbsl, summit 3385 mbsl
Perdido Hill (Colina Perdido)	Perdido	Elongated (19 x 10 km), height 300m, base n.a., summit 3990 mbsl

Summary of science operations:

From 1-15 December 2023, Octopus Odyssey (too) conducted twelve full-ocean depth ROV dives with ROV SuBastian, plus one aborted dive due to a ground fault, augmented by five full-ocean depth CTD Niskin Rosette casts, and multibeam operations resulting in 7416 km² of coverage in Costa Rican waters (Table 2, Figure 2).

We had roughly 104 hours of ROV operations (55 hours on the seafloor + 49 hours of ascent/descent; Table 3). This has currently resulted in approximately 141 hours of video and 330 video files ingested into Tator for video annotation, although several video files from early in the expedition were not exported properly to Tator; this is still being resolved by SOI as of the time of this writing. The longest ROV dive was a little over 16 hours and the deepest depth of ROV exploration was 3179 mbsl.

We had 241 sampling events with the ROV in the water: 93 primary biological specimens, 14 sediment push cores, 21 ROV Niskin samples, 20 rock samples, and 51 fluid samples collected with a third-party SUPR sampler (Table 4). On the ship, we collected an additional 66 secondary associate biological samples from primary specimens, bringing the total number of samples to 307 (this does not include subsamples). We also conducted 23 video transects.

Three third-party technologies were integrated into ROV SuBastian electronics to use on the expedition: (1) a heat-flow probe for measuring thermal gradients in sediment, (2) an Aanderaa dissolved oxygen probe with temperature sensor, and (3) a SUPR fluid sampling system. We also deployed a stand-alone HOBO dissolved oxygen probe with temperature sensor. We conducted 14 heat flow measurements, ten measurements of hydrothermal springs with the DO probe, and six dives with hydrothermal spring SUPR sampling events. In addition, a diversity of third-party experiments were deployed on and recovered from the seafloor, including autonomous temperature loggers, microbial colonization experiments (i.e. microbe traps), two types of animal shelters (i.e. clay pots and PVC joints), OsmoSamplers, and bags of wood. In total, 42 experiments were part of the sampling.

For the most part, our operations went according to schedule. No ROV operations were ended early due to operational issues, although one dive was aborted on launch due to a ground fault in a third-party instrument; this was quickly resolved and the dive restarted. One dive ended early due to a fishing long-line drifting towards the vessel; we recovered early then re-dove on the site after the long-line passed by. Communications with fishing boats and the fisheries ministry, enabled by the Berth-of-Opportunity Observer from Instituto Costarricense de Pesca y Acuicultura (INCOPESCA), helped prevent further issues in the area.

Table 2. Overview of Fkt231202 operations

			0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
Nov	30	Thu									Mobilization begins in Balboa, Panama															
Dec	1	Fri	Mobilization continues												underway											
Dec	2	Sat	Departure & Underway - 564 nm @ 8.5 kt = 67 hours																							
Dec	3	Sun	underway																							
Dec	4	Mon	underway											ROV Dive #1 - 619 - El Dorado Hill												
Dec	5	Tue	transit			ROV Dive #2 - 620 - La Pulperia Hill															CTD#1					
Dec	6	Wed	HydroMidE			621 - Tengosed Seamount						wait		622 - Tengosed Seamount												
Dec	7	Thu	CTD#2 HydroMidW			ROV Dives #5&6 - 623&624 - El Dorado Hill #2																				
Dec	8	Fri	CTD#3 HydroMidS			ROV Dive #7 - 625 - Caballito Knoll #1																				
Dec	9	Sat	CTD#4 HydroCenter			ROV Dive #8 - 626 - El Dorado Hill (BBC day)																				
Dec	10	Sun	CTD#5 HydroMidN			ROV Dive #9 - 627 - Caballito Knoll #2															multibeam					
Dec	11	Mon	multibeam			ROV Dive #10 - 628 - La Pulperia Hill #2															transit					
Dec	12	Tue	ROV Dive #11 - 629 - Tengosed Seamount #2						transit						ROV Dive #12											
Dec	13	Wed	630 - El Dorado Hill			transit			ROV Dive #13 - 631 - Fuente Knoll																	
Dec	14	Thu	Underway to port - 280 nm @ 8 kt = 35 hours																							
Dec	15	Fri	underway											Demobilization in Golfito, Costa Rica												
Dec	16	Sat												Transit to San José												

Table 3. Overview of all ROV Dives on Fkt231202

Dive ID	Location	Deck to Deck	Deployment	Descent	Seabed	Ascent	Recovery	Max Depth	Samples	
S0618	Panama - Flamenco	00d 00:23:53			00d 00:10:10			14.84m	0	
S0619	Dorado Outcrop	00d 11:46:26	00d 00:05:11	00d 02:16:34	00d 07:03:05	00d 02:03:47	00d 00:17:46	3017.8m	13	
S0620	La Pulperia	00d 15:58:48	00d 00:08:08	00d 02:06:01	00d 11:14:48	00d 02:12:58	00d 00:16:51	2856.9m	22	
S0621	Tengosed	00d 07:08:27	00d 00:10:44	00d 01:42:22	00d 03:32:32	00d 01:26:18	00d 00:16:29	2026.57m	10	
S0622	Tengosed	00d 07:51:32	00d 00:05:09	00d 01:32:20	00d 04:35:00	00d 01:16:33	00d 00:22:28	1927.72m	14	
S0623	Dorado Outcrop	00d 00:16:57	00d 00:05:37					22.31m	0	
S0624	Dorado Outcrop	00d 16:11:51	00d 00:06:49	00d 02:21:18	00d 11:24:10	00d 02:01:04	00d 00:18:28	3179.41m	33	
S0625	Caballito	00d 14:59:11	00d 00:07:10	00d 02:20:31	00d 10:16:06	00d 01:57:27	00d 00:17:55	3180.6m	13	
S0626	Dorado Outcrop	00d 16:53:32	00d 00:07:28	00d 02:28:43	00d 10:58:00	00d 02:59:52	00d 00:19:27	3025.9m	5	
S0627	Caballito	00d 15:12:38	00d 00:08:42	00d 02:19:48	00d 10:17:29	00d 02:06:08	00d 00:20:30	3177.92m	5	
S0628	La Pulperia	00d 15:20:31	00d 00:11:16	00d 02:08:50	00d 10:42:50	00d 02:02:58	00d 00:14:36	2883.08m	14	
S0629	Tengosed	00d 13:06:54	00d 00:06:15	00d 01:47:57	00d 09:34:28	00d 01:20:25	00d 00:17:48	2259.02m	21	
S0630	Dorado	00d 10:19:35	00d 00:06:24	00d 02:16:36	00d 05:30:36	00d 02:05:51	00d 00:20:06	3067.88m	20	
S0631	Fuente Knoll	00d 12:04:50	00d 00:05:40	00d 01:56:19	00d 07:56:58	00d 01:46:22	00d 00:19:30	2753.81m	18	
Totals	14 Dives	06d 13:35:12	00d 01:34:39	01d 01:17:23	04d 07:16:17	00d 23:19:49	00d 03:41:59	3180.6m	188	0

Table 4. Summary of number of primary samples taken on expedition.

B: Biological sample, R: Rock sample, S: Sediment push core sample, N: Niskin sample, F: SUPR fluid sample; E: Experiment recovery sample (i.e. OsmoSampler, Temp Logger, Microbe Trap, Animal Shelter, Wood Bag)

Dive	Site	B- In water	R	S	N	F	E	In water Total	B- On Ship	Total
619	El Dorado	3	1	0	2	12	7	25	3	27
620	La Pulpería	6	5	0	2	11	8	32	9	41
621	Tengosed	6	2	0	1	1	1	11	3	14
622	Tengosed #2	12	1	0	1	0	0	14	5	19
624	El Dorado #2	8	2	0	2	12	17	41	5	46
625	Caballito	12	0	8	1	0	0	21	20	41
626	El Dorado BBC	3	1	0	1	0	0	5	1	6
627	Near Caballito	2	0	6	3	0	0	11	0	11
628	La Pulpería	7	3	0	3	7	1	21	2	23
629	Tengosed #2	13	4	0	3	8	2	30	8	38
630	El Dorado #3	10	1	0	2	0	6	19	5	24
631	Fuente Knoll	11	2	5	2	0	0	20	5	25
TOTAL	-	93	20	14	21	51	42	241	66	307

Figure 2. Overview map of stations visited on Fkt231202, from MFP tool.

Top panel shows work area in relation to ports. Lower panel shows zoomed in view of working area. Purple circles represent ROV stations and blue circles represent CTD stations.

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Fkt231202 Cruise track from Rolling Deck to Repository

Summary of documentary filming operations

Two days of operational time were added to the Octopus Odyssey (too) expedition to allow a documentary film team from the BBC to join the expedition. The science party was given discretion on how to operationalize this time within the overall expedition, as filming needs in some cases depended on scientific operations and/or guidance. We choose to operationalize this as several blocks of time embedded within scientific dives plus one dedicated dive for filming, aiming to achieve 23 hours of bottom time or 32 hours of ROV operations (i.e. the equivalent of 2x 16-hour dive days assuming 11.5 hours on bottom each dive). The following lists the minimum time committed for this effort, *not including footage collected during ascent/descents*:

Table 5. Overview of ROV time committed to documentary filmmaking

Dive	Hours exclusive for BBC while ROV on bottom (i.e no livesteam)	Bonus hours for filming during science operations (i.e. livestream continued to broadcast)
619	1.5	0
620	1.5	0
621	0	0
622	0	0
624	3	1.5
625	0	0
626	12	0
627	0	0
628	3	1
629	0	0
630	0	1.5
631	0	0
TOTAL	21	4

Initial findings and potential impact of the research:

- 1) The biggest finding of the expedition was confirmation that the *Muusoctopus* nurseries offshore Costa Rica support baby octopus throughout the year, not just in the summer rainy season. Scientists onboard witnessed spectacular scenes of the first moments of life, as baby octopus emerged from their eggs, including traveling with one hatchling for an epic journey over 150 m up into the water. Immature eggs were also observed to have tiny octopus embryos inside. Having two expeditions to the same region in one year was essential for confirming this finding.
- 2) The seamounts offshore Costa Rica support at least four new species of deep-sea octopuses, based on the collection of specimens from both Octopus Odyssey expeditions in June and December 2023. This is an unprecedented biodiversity of octopus in this small area especially at these depths. The one species of the genus *Muusoctopus* that broods eggs in hydrothermal springs is similar to, but a separate species from, the species that broods eggs at hydrothermal springs around the Davidson Seamount offshore California. Scientists working on the taxonomic identification of this species propose the common name Dorado octopus, to distinguish it from the pearl octopus at Davidson Seamount. The other three species do not appear to brood their eggs in hydrothermal springs. On the Octopus Odyssey (too) expedition, the essential male specimen was collected to enable complete species description of a new *Graneledone* species.
- 3) Tengosed Seamount supports a skate nursery, evidenced by a mass of hundreds of skate eggs with embryos and observation of a pregnant skate visiting the area.
- 4) The water column above the hydrothermal springs and outcrop features supports an incredible biodiversity of life, including giant phantom jellies, glass octopus, iridescent comb jellies, and black swallower fish.
- 5) Nearly 160 deep-sea animal specimens collected on the Octopus Odyssey (too) expedition will enrich the collection of the Museum of Zoology at the University of Costa Rica and fuel scientific discovery. It is likely that many of the specimens collected represent new species and new records of known species for the region. The animals collected on the Octopus Odyssey expeditions are essential for understanding the biodiversity and biogeography of Costa Rica and the eastern tropical Pacific's deep-sea heritage. The connectivity among the deep-sea habitats within Costa Rica still remains to be explored, but thus far, every deep-sea feature explored has shown a remarkable and delicate diversity of life that has persisted for centuries, if not millennia.
- 6) Rock and sediment samples collected on the OctoOdyssey (too) expedition are revolutionizing the understanding of the complex geological origins and processes occurring on this part of the seafloor. Surprisingly, initial analysis of microfossils in sediments reveals that seafloor sediments are millions-of-years old, indicating strong currents, dissolution and scouring. In addition, fossils of beaked whales were found on numerous outcrops. All microfossils and macrofossils will be archived in the Paleontology collection at the Central American School of Geology at the University of Costa Rica for continued study, with additional mineralogical samples shared with the Global Marine Minerals Program at the U.S. Geological Society.
- 7) New technologies interfaced with ROV SuBastian, as well as experiments deployed on the seafloor in June and recovered on this expedition, enabled the science team to

confirm that the three different hydrothermal springs in this area have unique trends of oxygen and temperature, indicating different seafloor processes. Custom fluid sampling equipment allowed for collection of samples to study the microbiomes of these unique hydrothermal spring waters, to understand what functions microbes perform and how they connect to the microbiomes of animals living in these places.

- 8) Bathymetric and subbottom profile mapping conducted on the OctoOdyssey expeditions was used to define the diverse seafloor features in this region to then propose official names to GEBCO. This naming effort is being led by Costa Rican scientists in consultation with the Costa Rican Committee on Nomenclature. New bathymetric data from the Octopus Odyssey (too) expedition reveals that the Caballito Knoll used to be a much larger feature; at some point in the past it collapsed, likely triggering a local tsunami.

Table 6. Brief dive highlights from each dive

Dive	#	Location	Highlight
619	1	El Dorado Hill	Baby octopus confirmed, successful 1st trial of SUPR and DO probe, giant medusa on descent
620	2	La Pulpería Hill	Confirmed lower oxygen in vent fluids, glass octopus
621	3	Tengosed Seamount	Marker X vent, giant medusa & glass octopus on ascent
622	4	Tengosed Seamount	Witnessed birth of octopus from flipped rock, skate park
623	5	bounce	n.a.
624	6	El Dorado Hill	Birth and death of octopus
625	7	Caballito Knoll	Confirmed summit is sediment covered with exposed carbonate, collected two whale rostrum fossils, <i>Gonatus</i> squid with eggs
626	8	El Dorado Hill	(for BBC filming) tracked baby octopus 60+ m into water column, watched momma pull out a hatchling, fresh eggs with incomplete predation, fresh eggs had tiny embryos
627	9	Near Caballito	Confirmed heat flow patterns, <i>Graneledone</i> sp. male
628	10	La Pulpería Hill	Whale fossil, octocorals & seastar, Male octopus filming
629	11	Tengosed Seamount	14m cliff, flying spaghetti monster siphonophore
630	12	El Dorado Hill	Shrimp with eggs in venus vase sponges & octo escort
631	13	Fuente Knoll	Tripod fish, two new species of <i>Graneledone</i> octos

How will information be shared:

Communication of findings is a major objective of the Octopus Odyssey expeditions. Outreach to local communities and managers includes preparing an invited summary of the expedition and importance of deep-sea research, in Spanish, for distribution to the Costa Rican Ministry of Foreign Affairs. This was completed on 10 October, led by Sergio Cambroner. In addition, the team is preparing to present results of the expedition to international diplomats attending the UN Ocean Conference stakeholder meeting in San José, Costa Rica in June 2024 as part of an official side event. Finally, the team is planning a science symposium for December 2024 in Costa Rica to share findings of the expedition. Data will be made available on BCO-DMO under the program page for the Crustal Ocean Biosphere Research Accelerator (COBRA), which is a US National Science Foundation-funded program: <https://www.bco-dmo.org/program/856233>

Acknowledgements, Funding, and Permissions

Permission to conduct international Marine Scientific Research in Costa Rica's waters was given diplomatic consent by the Costa Rican Ministry of Foreign Affairs to the US Embassy (DNS-2023-0126). This basic research was conducted with the permission to access genetic and biochemical elements and resources of biodiversity or associated traditional knowledge given by the National Commission for the Management of Biodiversity (Comisión Nacional para la Gestión de la Biodiversidad, CONAGEBIO) of the Ministry of Environment and Energy (Ministerio de Ambiente y Energía, MINAE) of Costa Rica (Permit R-026-2023-OT-CONAGEBIO to Dr. Jorge Cortés-Núñez). We also acknowledge the prior informed consent of the Minister of Fisheries and Aquaculture, Mr. Heiner Méndez Barrientos of the Costa Rican Institute of Fisheries and Aquaculture (INCOPECA). **All publications and presentations should reference this permit information.** All specimens are archived at the Museum of Zoology at the University of Costa Rica.

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The science party thanks the berth-of-opportunity special personnel on the expedition Valeria Naranjo and Nixon Lara Quesada for shipboard assistance with specimen processing and interfacing with INCOPECA.

Personnel

This final shakedown cruise of the RV Falkor (too) had a “science party” of 20 academic professionals + 1 artist-at-sea from Columbia + 1 berth of opportunity for a Costa Rican govt agency representative + 1 berth of opportunity for a Costa Rican student. In addition, we were joined by Multimedia Correspondent Conor Ashleigh and three crew from the BBC. Within the 20-person academic team, 45% of participants were from Costa Rican institutions, 50% were from US institutions, and one person was from Trinidad.

Shipboard “Science Party”

Person	^	Role	Country - Institution	Email
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^ = Career Stage: E, early career professional; G, graduate student; P, Postdoc; S, senior scientist

Shorebased collaborators with Tator access

Shorebased	^	Role	Country - Institution	Email
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^ = Career Stage: E, early career professional; G, graduate student; P, Postdoc; S, senior scientist

SOI staffing

Department Heads:

- Captain: Allan (Al) Doyle
- Lead Technician: John Fulmer
- Chief Officer: Anthony McCann
- Chief Engineer: Dan Buehler
- Purser: Jessica Van Jaarsveldt
- AV/IT: Todor Gerasimov
- ROV Lead: Jason Rodriguez

Multimedia Correspondent:

- [Conor Ashleigh](#)

Multimedia Technician:

- [Sofya Pesternikova](#)

Berths of Opportunity:

- [Valeria Naranjo](#) (UCR student)
- [Nixon Lara-Quesada](#) (INCOPESCA)

Artist at Sea:

- [Diego Gamero](#)

Dive Summaries:

Figure 3. Example dive basket configuration for Fkt231202 dives.

View of basket for Dive 620. Front of porch to aft, port to starboard: holster for dissolved oxygen probe, holster for SOI high-temperature probe, SOI BioBox1, yellow milkcrate with Fast Flow OsmoSampler, milkcrate with light pack for BBC filming, holster for SUPR sampler & Excalibur, milkcrate with flow concentrator cap and scoop and HOBO Dissolved Oxygen logger, SOI large BioBox. Port rail: sediment push cores. Starboard rail: coral quivers and suction sampler. Mounted on decking, straddling the SCI camera: SUPR sampler valves, electronics, and bottles. Mounted on port side top: Niskin bottles. Mounted on starboard side top: heat flow probe.

Dive S0619 - El Dorado Hill #1

Date: 4 December 2023

Time on bottom: 7 hours 3 minutes

of samples collected: 25 in water + 3 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#)

Dive track: This dive focused on revisiting Marker W on the southern end of Dorado Outcrop

Overview: The highlight of this dive was confirming that El Dorado Hill octopus nurseries are active in December. We witnessed the birth of baby octopus, unprompted by our direct activities. The nursery had several males and females interacting; we collected one specimen. We recovered several experiments that were deployed in June 2023, successfully used the SUPR sampler to collect fluid samples, and made dissolved oxygen measurements with the Aanderaa probe. The dive ended on schedule after completing operations. Another bucket-list highlight was seeing a phantom jelly during descent. Vehicle notes: slurp sampler not working, heat flow probe groundfault, oil leak on heat flow ram, divider in biobox 3 came out.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-04 19:18	Phantom jelly 1528 m	
2023-12-04 20:29	View of Markers R and W	
2023-12-04 20:45	First view of octopus egg with embryo	
2023-12-04 20:49	View of mother octopus with fresher undeveloped eggs	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-04 21:31</p>	<p>Octopus interaction</p>	
<p>2023-12-04 21:39</p>	<p>First view of octopus baby being born</p>	
<p>2023-12-04 21:55</p>	<p>Even more octopus interaction</p>	
<p>2023-12-04 21:59</p>	<p>Octopus closeup</p>	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-04 22:21</p>	<p>Marker W temperature measurement - 11.9C, 56 μM O₂</p>	
<p>2023-12-04 22:47</p>	<p>SUPR fluid sampling (5C)</p>	
<p>2023-12-05 00:37</p>	<p>Another octopus baby</p>	
<p>2023-12-05 01:33</p>	<p>Octopus collection</p>	

Dive S0620 - La Pulpería Hill #1

Date: 5 December 2023

Time on bottom: 11 hours 14 minutes

of samples collected: 32 in water + 9 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#)

Dive track: This dive focused on visiting the Marker Q vent area on the north side of the pinnacle at the top of La Pulpería Hill.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was the recovery and deployment of experiments at Marker Q, collection of vent fluids from an animal-rich area with the SUPR sampler, and seeing a glass octopus on ascent. There was a very strong current throughout the dive. The dive ended on schedule after objectives had been accomplished. Vehicle notes: CTD groundfault, Heat flow ground fault, high temperature probe ground fault after first measurement, insert came out of BioBox 3

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-05 13:29	Flyover Marker Q	<p>HEADING 208 ° O2 CON. 136 µM O2 SAL. 34.1 % 2023-12-05 13:28:53 UTC</p>
2023-12-05 15:00	View of experiments at Marker Q. Note that intake had fallen out for Pink OsmoSampler.	<p>HEADING 200 ° O2 CON. 130 µM O2 SAL. 34.8 % 2023-12-05 15:00:23 UTC</p>
2023-12-05 15:25	Collection of wood bag and microbe traps at Marker Q	<p>HEADING 200 ° High-Temperature Probe O2 CON. 130 µM 2.34 °C O2 SAL. 34.8 % Max (Past Minute): 2.94 ° 2023-12-05 15:20:22 UTC</p> <p>HEADING 202 ° High-Temperature Probe O2 CON. 130 µM 1.46 °C O2 SAL. 34.8 % Max (Past Minute): 1.76 ° 2023-12-05 15:25:58 UTC</p>

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-05 16:43</p>	<p>Collection of zoarcid fish from below Marker Q</p>	
<p>2023-12-05 17:18</p>	<p>Temperature at vent below Marker Q 4.5C and 89 µM oxygen (note: spot of SUPR sample, and rock collected on Dive 628)</p>	
<p>2023-12-05 18:12</p>	<p>SUPR sampling from vent below Marker Q</p>	
<p>2023-12-05 18:46</p>	<p>Octopus versus lobster</p>	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-05 20:34</p>	<p>Deployment of Yellow OsmoSampler at Marker Q</p>	
<p>2023-12-05 20:39</p>	<p>HOBO DO probe deployment</p>	
<p>2023-12-05 21:07</p>	<p>Collection of octopus & eggs at marker Q</p>	
<p>2023-12-05 23:48</p>	<p>Sponge collected for BBC filming</p>	

<p>2023-12-06 02:00</p>	<p>Glass octopus in lower OMZ at 932 m, oxygen concentration 30 μM</p>	
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Dive S0621 - Tengosed Seamount #1

Date: 6 December 2023

Time on bottom: 3 hours 32 minutes

of samples collected: 11 in water + 3 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#)

Dive track: This dive focused on visiting the Marker X vent site.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was recovery of experiments at Marker X and several water column wonders including a **Deepstaria**, a **Giant Phantom Jelly**, and **Glass Octopus**. Attempts to collect dissolved oxygen measurements and SUPR vent fluid samples were not fruitful due to the depth of the vent below the vehicle. Dive ended early before completing objectives due to long lines drifting toward vessel. Vehicles notes: CTD ground fault.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-06 13:16	Recovery of Marker X temp logger	
2023-12-06 13:43	Marker X vent temperature and DO measurement, 2.4C and 92.2 µM	
2023-12-06 13:53	Deploy OsmoSampler at Marker X vent. Note: SUPR intake not long enough so did not sample fluids at this site.	
2023-12-06 15:43	Sampling rock ledge and ooze near Marker X	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-06 17:03</p>	<p><i>Deepstaria lobate</i> jelly (1261 m)</p>	
<p>2023-12-06 17:06</p>	<p><i>Stygiomedusa gigantea</i> Giant Phantom Jelly (1196 m)</p>	
<p>2023-12-06 17:13</p>	<p><i>Thalassocalyce</i> ctenophore (1033 m)</p>	
<p>2023-12-06 17:29</p>	<p>Glass octopus <i>Vitreledonella</i> (collected) - 701m</p>	

Dive S0622 - Tengosed Seamount #2

Date: 6 December 2023

Time on bottom: 4 hours 35 minutes

of samples collected: 14 in water + 5 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#)

Dive track: This short dive focused on exploring around the Skate Park area of Tengosed

Overview: The highlight of this dive was witnessing the birth of several octopus babies at the base of Skate Park, and observing a presumably pregnant skate (i.e. with crooked tail) gliding towards Skate Park. This was a short dive on Skate Park, delayed by long-line fishing in the area. The dive ended once objectives were completed. Video transects were collected around Skate Park, but there was again not clear evidence for hydrothermal venting.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-06 23:02	White back Muusoctopus octopus hiding under a rock at the base of the summit of Skate Park	<p>HEADING 785 O2 CON. 108 μM O2 SAT. 28.7 % DEPTH 1916 m SALINITY 34.6 PSU TEMP. 2.35 °C 2023-12-06 23:02:46 UTC</p>
2023-12-06 23:13	Relocating Skate Park	<p>O2 CON. 107 μM O2 SAT. 28.5 % DEPTH 1893 m SALINITY 34.6 PSU TEMP. 2.37 °C 2023-12-06 23:15:39 UTC</p>
2023-12-06 23:21	Possible corallivory	<p>O2 CON. 107 μM O2 SAT. 28.5 % DEPTH 1893 m SALINITY 34.6 PSU TEMP. 2.37 °C 2023-12-06 23:21:16 UTC</p>
2023-12-06 23:48	Skate eggs at Skate Park	<p>O2 CON. 107 μM O2 SAT. 28.5 % DEPTH 1893 m SALINITY 34.6 PSU TEMP. 2.38 °C PT O2 CON. 83.7 μM PT O2 SAT. 28.6 % 2023-12-06 23:50:28 UTC</p>

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-17 01:44</p>	<p>Revisit of octopus for sampling</p>	
<p>2023-12-17 01:52</p>	<p>Babies hatching!</p>	
<p>2023-12-07 02:19</p>	<p>Observation of presumably pregnant skate at the Skate Park</p>	

Dive S0624 - El Dorado Hill #2 (Dive 623 was scrubbed)

Date: 7 December 2023

Time on bottom: 11 hours 24 minutes

of samples collected: 41 in water + 5 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#)

Dive track: This dive started in the abyssal plain to the SW of Markers K/R/W for a heat flow measurement, then visited the nodule field on the slope, then conducted transects up the slope, then ended at Marker R.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was observing the interaction and predation of an octopus carcass at Marker R, and recovery of experiments. This dive went according to schedule and ended when objectives were completed. Vehicle notes: Groundfault on SUPR on Launch of Dive 623, so recovered, tightened fittings and back in the water for Dive 624. 2 Hours for BBC filming.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-07 15:09	Recover Microbe Traps from Marker nodule area downslope of Markers	
2023-12-07 17:04	Recovery of wood bag from Marker W	
2023-12-07 17:34	Baby octopus at marker R	
2023-12-07 17:34	Dead octopus by octopus at Marker R	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-07 17:55</p>	<p>Recovery of Microbe Traps from Marker R (with octo interactions in the background)</p>	
<p>2023-12-07 18:41</p>	<p>Recovery of temperature logger from Marker R (with attached octopus)</p>	
<p>2023-12-07 19:02</p>	<p>DO 56 µM Marker R, temp 12C</p>	
<p>2023-12-07 19:13</p>	<p>SUPR fluid sampling of Marker R (with octo slapping shrimp away and shrimp eating dead octopus)</p>	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-07 21:22</p>	<p>Shrimp eating dead octopus</p>	
<p>2023-12-07 23:02</p>	<p>View of hectocotylus of male octopus</p>	
<p>2023-12-07 23:45</p>	<p>Corals sampled for challenge experiments</p>	
<p>2023-12-08 01:30</p>	<p>Crinoid fight (missing from tator)</p>	

Dive S0625 - Caballito Knoll #1

Date: 8 December 2023

Time on bottom: 10 hours 16 minutes

of samples collected: 21 in water + 20 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: This dive started in the abyssal plain for heat flow measurement, then moved up the summit while conducting transects.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was observing two dumbo octopus, two whale rostrums, a skate, and *Gonatus* squid with eggs in the water column. As before, this seafloor feature is covered in sediment with almost no rock exposures, although there was exposed carbonate ooze at the top. The focus of this dive started with heat flow measurements, sediment specimen sampling, and video transects. The dive ended early due to long-line fishing interference. Vehicle issues: SPRING Comms down surround 22:45 so no USBL aiding, had to rerun reports; M3 sonar acting up.

Notable events:

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-08	Start dive with heat flow	
2023-12-08 15:08	Dumbo octopus	
2023-12-08 18:41	Brisingid sea star	
2023-12-08 20:43	skate	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-08 20:54</p>	<p>Whale rostrum fossil</p>	
<p>2023-12-08 21:29</p>	<p>Second dumbo octopus</p>	
<p>2023-12-08 21:34</p>	<p>Second whale rostrum</p>	
<p>2023-12-09 00:46</p>	<p><i>Gonatus</i> squid with eggs</p>	

Dive S0626 - El Dorado Hill (BBC)

Date: 9 December 2023

Time on bottom: 10 hours 58 minutes

of samples collected: 5 in water + 1 on ship

Divestream links: not live streamed because video was embargoed for BBC

Dive track: this dive focused on the marker K/R/W area for filming.

Overview: This dive was exclusively for BBC filming, with science party on standby to advise and direct sampling. By spending dedicated time observing octopus behaviors, we learned more about octopus ecophysiology, including that octopus are laying fresh eggs, that eggs and octopus carcasses are not always consumed right away, that nearby mothers ventilate the water around exposed eggs (presumably to push scent away or to ensure ample oxygen available to them?), that baby octopus can swim at least 60 m into the water column after hatching, that skin from the suckers comes off when octopus clean themselves. The dive ended on schedule after objectives were completed. Vehicle issues: Lost SPRINT comms for whole dive

Notable events

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-09 14:23	Close up of defecating shrimp	A close-up photograph of a shrimp, likely a cleaner shrimp, positioned on a dark, rocky surface. The shrimp is oriented vertically, and its body is illuminated, showing its translucent, pinkish-orange hue. The background is dark and out of focus.
2023-12-09 15:02	Shrimp posing in foreground in front of octopus cleaning	A photograph showing two shrimp in the foreground, one of which is posing. In the background, an octopus is visible, appearing to be cleaning or interacting with the shrimp. The scene is set on a dark, rocky substrate.
2023-12-09 15:03	Removal of mother octopus from fresh egg clutch	A photograph capturing a mother octopus using its beak to remove a fresh egg clutch from a dark, rocky surface. The egg clutch is a cluster of small, white, oval-shaped eggs.
2023-12-09 15:13	Eggs exposed	A close-up photograph of a large, white, oval-shaped egg clutch, likely belonging to an octopus, resting on a dark, rocky surface. The eggs are arranged in a dense, fan-like pattern.

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-09 15:29</p>	<p>Lots of shrimp on eggs</p>	
<p>2023-12-09 15:45</p>	<p>Cutthroat eel eating eggs</p>	
<p>2023-12-09 16:11</p>	<p>Fresh-ish eggs from <i>Muusoctopus</i> by Marker R (suction sampling later showed very small embryos in some)</p>	
<p>2023-12-09 18:27</p>	<p>Baby octopus jetting up into the water column over 60m</p>	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-09 20:58</p>	<p>Confirmation of male octopus</p>	A male octopus with a reddish-pink body and long, thin tentacles is resting on a dark, rocky seabed. The octopus is positioned in the center of the frame, facing towards the right.
<p>2023-12-10 00:25</p>	<p>Rock sample</p>	A close-up view of a rock sample being collected. A metal grabber is shown on the left, holding a piece of dark rock. A green tag with the letter 'R' is visible in the background, along with several small, glowing blue organisms.
<p>2023-12-10 01:57</p>	<p>Jelly with parasites (1486 m)</p>	A close-up view of a jellyfish, likely a comb jelly, with a translucent body and long, thin tentacles. The jellyfish is covered in numerous small, yellowish-brown parasites, which are visible as small, curved structures on its surface.
<p>2023-12-10 02:13</p>	<p>Siphonophore (1220 m)</p>	A close-up view of a purple siphonophore, a colonial invertebrate. It has a long, curved body with a purple hue and several long, thin tentacles extending from the bottom.

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-10 02:45</p>	<p>Glass octopus <i>Vitreledonella</i> (802 m)</p>	
<p>2023-12-10 03:10</p>	<p>Pelagic larvae of anemone (507 m)</p>	

Dive S0627 - Near Caballito Knoll

Date: 10 December 2023

Time on bottom: 10 hours 17 minutes

of samples collected: 11 in water + 0 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: This dive focused on heat flow measurements in the abyssal plain between Caballito Knoll and La Pulpería Hill.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was stumbling across a male *Graneledone* sp. octopus at the final heat flow station of the dive, which will allow describing the new species. This dive focused on heat flow measurements between Caballito and La Pulpería, with opportunistic sampling for other tasks.

Notable events

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-10 16:39	Irregular sea urchin during heat flow	
2023-12-10 22:42	Male <i>Graneledone</i> sp.	
2023-12-10 23:52	Push core mania	

Dive S0628 - La Pulpería Hill

Date: 11 December 2023

Time on bottom: 10 hours 42 minutes

of samples collected: 21 in water + 2 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: This dive started to the west of Marker Q in an area with an escarpment, then transited to the summit to visit Marker Q.

Overview: The highlights of this dive was additional fluid sampling at Marker Q, watching a male *Muusoctopus* at the summit of La Pulpería, collecting another whale rostrum, and collection of a new sea star. The dive ended after objectives had been completed and according to schedule.

Notable events

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-11 13:19	Escarpment on La Pulperia (sampled ledge and ooze)	
2023-12-11 14:37	Female <i>Muusoctopus</i> (for film) in flight from summit of La Pulperia	
2023-12-11 15:38	Male <i>Muustoctopus</i> (for film) at summit of La Pulperia	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-11 18:29</p>	<p>Collection of whale rostrum on way to La Pulperia summit</p>	
<p>2023-12-11 18:49</p>	<p>Sea star collected</p>	
<p>2023-12-11 20:05</p>	<p>Collection of brooding <i>Muusoctopus</i> above Marker Q</p>	
<p>2023-12-11 20:24</p>	<p>Collection of <i>Muusocotpus</i> eggs</p>	

<p>2023-12-11 21:28</p>	<p>DO measurements at vent below Marker Q, where Fast Flow OsmoSampler had been</p>	
<p>2023-12-11 23:17</p>	<p>SUPR sampling below Marker Q vent, where Fast Flow OsmoSampler had been</p>	

Dive S0629 - Tengosed Seamount #3

Date: 12 December 2023

Time on bottom: 9 hours 34 minutes

of samples collected: 30 in water + 8 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: This dive started on the edge of the summit of Tengosed Seamount in an area that had not been explored before, then transited to an escarpment, and then ended at Marker X.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was the successful sampling and sensing of the venting fluids from Marker X, and sighting of a flying spaghetti monster siphonophore on recovery. The dive started an hour ahead of schedule, and the extra time was used to opportunistically sample an escarpment of carbonate ooze for age dating. Vehicle issues: One of the manipulator masters is dead, so the one remaining master had to be switched for port and starboard operations.

Notable events

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-12	Glass squid (704 m)	A close-up photograph of a glass squid being held by a robotic arm. The squid is transparent with a yellowish-orange internal structure. The robotic arm is metallic and has a blue and yellow logo on it.
2023-12-12	<i>Japetella</i> (732 m)	A photograph of a Japetella jellyfish, which is a large, bell-shaped jellyfish with a translucent body and a reddish-brown center. It is shown against a dark background.
2023-12-12 09:37	Coral and friends	A photograph of a coral reef. The reef is covered in various types of coral, including branching and table corals. The water is clear and blue.
2023-12-12 10:37	Cool urchin	A photograph of a red sea urchin. The urchin is spherical and covered in long, dark spines. It is being held by a robotic arm.

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<p>2023-12-12 12:00</p>	<p>14m tall scarp, sampled in a vertical transect for dating</p>	
<p>2023-12-12 15:24</p>	<p>SUPR sampling of Marker X vent</p>	
<p>2023-12-12 17:28</p>	<p>Recovery of Fast Flow OsmoSampler from Marker X</p>	
<p>2023-12-12 17:38</p>	<p>Lowering HOBO DO probe into Marker X vent</p>	

2023-12-12 19:16	Flying spaghetti monster siphonophore (1232 m)	

Dive S0630 - El Dorado Hill Marker A

Date: 13 December 2023

Time on bottom: 5 hours 30 minutes

of samples collected: 19 in water + 5 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#)

Dive track: This dive focused on visiting the Marker A area on the northwestern end of the El Dorado Hill.

Overview: The highlight of this dive was recovery of experiments from Marker A, although venting was diminished during the dive (as also recorded by the temperature logger that was recovered). Another highlight was the view of shrimp with eggs inside of venus vase sponges. An octopus escorted our departure from seafloor of El Dorado. The dive ended after objectives were accomplished. Vehicle issues: one manipulator master still down, so having to switch masters between manipulators.

Notable events

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-13 05:19	No joy for SUPR sampling at Marker A, no venting	An underwater photograph showing a diver's arm and a marker labeled 'A' on the seafloor. The seafloor is dark and appears to be covered in sediment or silt. The marker is a small white flag on a thin pole. The diver's arm is visible on the left side of the frame, and some equipment is visible on the right.
2023-12-13 06:55	Octopus interaction (for filming)	An underwater photograph showing an octopus interacting with a purple, textured object. The octopus is on the left, and the purple object is on the right. The background is dark, suggesting an underwater environment.
2023-12-13 09:26	Nice shot of octopus and sponge cluster on El Dorado	An underwater photograph showing an octopus near a large green sponge cluster. The octopus is on the left, and the sponge cluster is on the right. The background is dark, suggesting an underwater environment.
2023-12-13 09:45	Venus vase sponge with shrimp inside with eggs	An underwater photograph showing Venus vase sponges with shrimp inside. The sponges are white and have a porous, vase-like structure. The shrimp are visible inside the sponges. The background is dark, suggesting an underwater environment.

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-13 09:54</p>	<p>Octopus escort as we leave El Dorado for the last time on this expedition. Until we meet again.</p>	
<p>2023-12-13</p>	<p>Recovery at sunrise</p>	

Dive S0631 - Fuente Knoll (bonus dive)

Date: 13 December 2023

Time on bottom: 7 hours 56 minutes

of samples collected: 21 on seafloor + 20 on ship

Divestream links: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#)

Dive track: This dive visited the Fuente Knoll, starting in the area of a known escarpment and then exploring sites that had not been visited on the previous expedition.

Overview: There were several highlights on this dive: spectacular mid-water creatures, a tripod fish, a stalked crinoid, perhaps two different *Graneledone* spp. octopus, and collection of another beaked whale fossil. The dive went according to schedule and ended when objectives were completed.

Noteable events

Date & Time	Event	Image
2023-12-13	Glass octopus (231 m)	
2023-12-13 16:48	Pteropod (1023 m)	
2023-12-13 17:06	Bottle brush siphonophore (1192 m)	
2023-12-13 17:12	Comb jelly (1347 m)	

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-13 18:25</p>	<p>escarpment</p>	A photograph showing a deep-sea escarpment. The seafloor is covered in a dense, greenish-brown microbial mat. A robotic arm is visible in the upper left corner, and a white object is in the upper right corner.
<p>2023-12-13 20:20</p>	<p>Stalked crinoid with gastropod associate</p>	A photograph of a stalked crinoid. The crinoid has a long, thin, brown stalk and a cluster of yellow, feathery arms at the top. A small, brown, shell-like object (gastropod) is attached to the base of the crinoid's arms.
<p>2023-12-13 21:24</p>	<p>Tripod fish!</p>	A photograph of a tripod fish. The fish is white with a dark stripe along its side and is swimming in a dark, greenish water column. Its three long, thin legs are extended downwards.
<p>2023-12-13 23:05</p>	<p><i>Graneledone</i> sp. octopus specimen</p>	A photograph showing a white octopus specimen being collected. The octopus is on a rocky, greenish-brown seafloor. A yellow mesh net is being used to capture it. A robotic arm is visible in the upper right corner.

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

<p>2023-12-13 23:36</p>	<p>Another graneledone sp.</p>	
<p>2023-12-14 00:03</p>	<p>Sea cucumber collection</p>	
<p>2023-12-14 01:35</p>	<p>Beaked whale fossil</p>	
<p>2023-12-14 02:02</p>	<p>Octo send off (another new species??)</p>	

Daily plans

Thursday 30 November (on EST)

- 06:15 - Hotel pickup for Tantaló group
- 06:30 - Hotel pickup for Cascades group
- 07:00 - Clear immigration
- 07:30 - Transport to Flamenco marina
- 08:00 - Board vessel and move in to berthing
- 10:00 - safety orientation
- 12:30 - ship tour
- 14:30 - science party meeting to discuss lab setup
- 17:00 - science party introduction to MMC/MMT

Friday 1 December (on EST)

- 09:00 - ROV overview @ hangar
- 10:30 - co-chiefs meeting with film/outreach leads @ conference room
- 13:00 - science party meeting followed by specimen protocol overview
- 15:30 - emergency drills
- 15:45 - underway!
- 17:30 - departure BBQ on outdoor lounge
- 19:00 - OctoOdyssey videos @ mess
- NOTE: clocks going backwards one hour at 2AM!! (2AM becomes 1AM)

Saturday 2 December

- BLOG #2 due to Beth (Huber & Ramírez)
- 09:15 - Livestream training for science party @ conference room
- 10:00 - Science talks for crew part 1 @ mess
- 13:00 - Science party meeting @ conference room
- 15:00 - Science talks for crew part 2 @ mess
- 19:00 - PIPA update by Rotjan @ mess

Sunday 3 December

- CABIN CLEANING & INSPECTION DAY
- 02:45 - Entered Costa Rica EEZ and begin turning on sensors
- 08:45 - SeaLog training for science (new people mandatory, June crew optional)
- 10:00 - Science talks for crew part 1 @ mess
- 13:00 - Science meeting @ conference room
- 14:00 - Engine room tour (wear closed toe shoes and long pants)
- 15:00 - Science talks for crew part 2 @ mess
- 16:30 - Tator training @ conference room
- 19:00 - Presentation by captain @ mess

Monday 4 December

- ~12:00 - arrival on station at Dorado Outcrop, begin ROV Dive S0619 (12 hour dive)

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- 16:00 - Ship-to-Shore (Spanish) with UCR Reef Fishes classes (Valeria lead)
- 20:30 - science party meeting in main lab

Tuesday 5 December

- 00:00 - ROV recovery & begin transit to La Pulpería, with crossing line over Dorado for subbottom profiler (SBP)
 - WP1 for SBP: 9.09722 / -87.08889
 - WP2 for SBP: 9.0533 / -87.1167
 - WP3 for dive location: 8.6217 / -87.2796
- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive S0620 at La Pulpería (16 hour dive)
- 10:30 - Ship-to-shore (English) with Lincoln Middle School, Boston (Rotjan lead)
- 14:00 - COBRA co-Is host COBRA webinar!
- 19:00 - Science party meeting in main lab
- 21:00 - Recover ROV, begin 24 nm transit for CTD#1 HydroMidE (8.9462 / -87.0407)

Wednesday 6 December

- 00:00 - Launch CTD#1
- 02:30 - Recovery CTD#1, begin 12 nm transit to Tengosed
- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive 621 at Tengosed
 - *Dive ended early due to long lines in the area*
- ~~19:00 - Science party meeting~~
- ~~21:00 - Recover ROV, begin 12 nm transit to CTD #2 HydroMidCenter (8.9859 / -87.1026, 3200m)~~
- ~~22:30 - Launch CTD #2~~
- 11:30 - Team bio meeting
- 12:30 - Recover ROV Dive 621 early due to long lines, then wait 1.5 hours
- 15:00 - Launch ROV Dive 622 Tengosed
- 16:00 - Science party meeting in main lab
- 23:00 - Recover ROV, begin transit to CTD#2 HydroMidW (9.0201 / -87.1612, 3165m)

Thursday 7 December

- 01:00 - Launch CTD #2 HydroMidW
- 03:30 - Recover CTD #2, begin 6 nm transit to Dorado Outcrop (9.0847 / -87.0961)
- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive 623 (bounce) and Dive 624 (45 minutes later)
- 10:00 - ~~Ship to shore with UNED remote high schools - canceled by UNED~~
- 20:00 - Science party meeting
- 22:00 - Recover ROV and begin 12 nautical mile transit to CTD #3 HydroMidS (8.9039 / -87.1768, 3210 m)
- 23:30 - Launch CTD#3

Friday 8 December - HALFWAY POINT

- 02:00 - Recover CTD #3, complete 20 nautical mile transit to Caballito (8.6375 / -87.3315, 3181 m)
- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive 625 at Caballito

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- 16:00 - Ship-to-shore with CIMAR + general public
- 19:00 - Science party meeting
- 20:10 - Recover ROV Dive 625
- ~~- 21:00 - Recover ROV Dive 625 (ended early due to long line)~~
- 20:30 - Begin setting up for subbottom profile across Caballito and La Pulpería
 - Start: 8.60247 / -87.36948
 - End: 8.63390 / -87.25615
- 22:00 - Begin 26 nautical mile transit to CTD #4 HydroCenter (8.9859 / -87.1026, 3200m)

Saturday 9 December

- 01:00 - Launch CTD #4
- 03:30 - Recover CTD #4, complete 6 nautical mile transit to Dorado (9.0825 / -87.0954, 3002 m)
- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive 626 at Dorado (BBC only)
- 15:00 - Ship-to-shore w/ Sustainable Ocean Alliance + Pelagos
- ~~- 17:00 - Ship-to-shore w/ Art Basel~~
- 19:00 - Science party meeting (tentative)
- 21:00 - Recover ROV (*on deck late due to water column filming*)
- 22:00 - Launch CTD#5 HydroMidN (9.0935 / -87.0221, 3184 m)

Sunday 10 December

- 00:30 - Recover CTD#5 (delayed)
- 06:00 - Launch ROV Dive 627 near Caballito (8.6200 / -87.3150, 3154 m)
- 10:30 - Cabin inspections
- 14:45 - Group photo on aft deck, then engine room tour
- 15:00 - Diego's YouTube Livestream
- 19:00 - Science party meeting
- 21:00 - Recover ROV, begin multibeam around Caballito + La Pulpería

Monday 11 December

- 05:00 - Launch ROV Dive 628 La Pulpería #2 (15 hour dive)
- 15:00 - Ship-to-Shore with INCOPECA
- 18:30 - Science meeting in conference room
- 20:00 - ROV on deck, transit to Tengosed

Tuesday 12 December

- 02:00 - Launch ROV Dive 629 Tengosed #2 (12 hour dive)
- 12:30 - Science meeting
- 14:00 - ROV on deck, transit to Dorado
- 20:00 - Launch ROV Dive 630 Dorado #3 (10 hour dive)

Wednesday 13 December

- 06:00 - Recover ROV, transit to Fuente

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- 10:00 - Ship-to-shore CR national academy
- 10:00 - Launch ROV Dive 631 Fuente (12 hour dive). Coordinates 8.7973 / -87.1740, 2703m
- 13:00 - co-chiefs meeting about UNOC + DOSI
- 20:30 - Science meeting in conference room
- 22:15 - ROV on deck, begin transit to port

Thursday 14 December

- Underway
- 09:00 - co-chiefs interview with Parley
- 10:00 - Science meeting in conference room - everyone presents update
- 12:30 - Co-chiefs debrief with SOI
- 13:30 - galley tour
- 14:00 - Open House ship-to-shore (Naranjo and Cambronero)
- 17:00 - Cruise reports due!
- 17:30 - Farewell celebration + BBQ

Friday 15 December

- 09:00 - Offloading of Huber and Orcutt containers, lab cleaning
- 13:00 - VIP tour
- 18:30 - post cruise celebration at marina restaurant

Saturday 16 December

- 06:00 - move out of cabins for inspections, luggage in muster area
- 07:00 - cabin inspections
- 07:30 - offload UCR gear, samples, and luggage and pack in shuttle and truck
- 08:00 - depart for San José

Biology/Animal Specimen Summary

Samples

ROV SuBastian collected a total of 159 biological samples for taxonomic identification and ground truthing of identifications from images (Table 7). Most samples were collected from Tengosed Seamount (n=46), followed by Dorado Outcrop (n=38). Of the 159 samples, 94 were primary samples and 65 were subsamples. This included 14 octopus samples: 10 adult specimens and four samples of eggs. Echinoderms were the most collected taxonomic group (n=35), followed by octocorals (n=27). All specimens are archived at the Museum of Zoology in Costa Rica. Further identification of collected specimens will be led by scientists from Universidad de Costa Rica in collaboration with international experts on morphological taxonomy. The majority of these samples were not collected during Fkt20230602. It is without doubt that many of the specimens collected are new species and/or new records for Costa Rica.

Table 7. Taxonomic groupings of primary biological specimens collected (not including associates).

* *Samples not recovered.*

Taxonomic ID	Caballito	El Dorado	Fuente	La Pulperia	Tengosed	Total
Anemone					1	1
Actiniaria sp.					1	1
Annelida	6	2	2	4	2	16
Amphinomidae sp.				3		3
Annelida sp.	1					1
Polychaeta sp.	2	1		1	2	6
Polynoidae sp.	1					1
Serpulidae sp.	2	1				3
Terebellidae sp.			1			1

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<i>Teuthidodrillus</i> sp.			1			1
Antipatharia					4	4
Antipatharia sp.					2	2
Schizopathidae sp.					1	1
<i>Umbellapathes</i> sp.					1	1
Cephalopoda (total)	1	5	1	5	3	15
<i>Graneledone</i> sp.	1					1
<i>Muusocotpus</i> sp. Egg cement				1		1
<i>Muusocotpus</i> type 1 (Dorado)		5		4		9
<i>Muusocotpus</i> type 2 or 3 or 4			1			1
<i>Muusocotpus</i> type 3					2	2
<i>Vitreledonella</i> cf. <i>richardi</i>					1	1
Crustacea		4	1	3	2	10
<i>Alvinocaris</i> sp.				1	0	1
Amphipoda sp.		2				2
Arthropoda sp.					2	1
Caprellidae sp.		1				1
Caridea sp.		1				1
Cirripedia sp.				1		1
Isopoda sp.			1			1
<i>Spongicoloides</i> sp.				1		1
Echinodermata	11	6	5	2	11	35
<i>Ophiuroidea</i> *					1	1
Amphilepidida sp.	1	1	1	1	1	5
Amphiuridae sp.	1	1				2
Brisingidae sp.	1					1
Cidaridae sp.	1					1
Crinoidea sp.		2				2
<i>Cystechinus loveni</i>	1					1
Echinothuriidae sp.					1	1
Euryalida sp.					2	2
Freyellidae sp.	1					1
Goniasteridae sp.		1				1
Holothuroidea sp.			1			1
<i>Hymenaster</i> sp.	1	1				2
Hyocrinidae sp.			1			1
Molpadidae sp.	1					1
Ophiacanthidae sp.					4	4
Ophiurida sp.	1					1
Persiculida sp.	1					1
<i>Solaster</i> cf. <i>pacificus</i>			1			1

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Synallactidae sp.	1		1			2
<i>Urechinus</i> sp.					1	1
Valvatida sp.				1		1
Hydrozoa	2			1		3
cf. Corymorphidae sp.	1					2
Hydrozoa sp.	1			1		2
Mollusca	5	4	1		3	13
Anomiidae sp.	1					1
<i>Berthella</i> sp.		1				1
Brachiopoda sp.	2					2
cf. <i>Idas</i> sp.					1	1
Gastropoda sp.	2				1	3
Pleuromariidae sp.			1			1
Polyplocophora sp.		3			1	4
Octocorallia	1	7	2	5	12	27
<i>Octocorallia</i> *					1	1
<i>Acanthagorgia</i> sp.					1	1
<i>Alcyonium</i> sp.		2		1	1	4
<i>Anthomastus</i> sp.		1		1	1	3
<i>Callozostrum</i> cf. <i>carlottae</i>	1					1
<i>Calyptrophora</i> sp.					1	1
Chrsyogorgiidae sp.			2		1	3
Corallidae sp.				1		1
Malacalcyonacea sp.		1				1
<i>Narella</i> sp.				1	2	3
<i>Paragorgia</i> sp.				1	2	3
Pennatulacea sp.		1				1
<i>Swiftia</i> sp.					1	1
<i>Thouarella</i> sp.		2				2
Porifera	2	7	1	2	3	15
Eupletellidae sp.				1		1
Hexactinellida sp.		2				2
Hyalonematidae sp.	1					1
Porifera sp.	1	5	1	1	3	11
Zoantharia		1				1
Zoanthidae sp.		1				1
Other taxa	6	1	2	3	5	18
Ascidiacea sp.		1				1
<i>Bathyraja</i> cf. <i>spinossisima</i>					5	5
Brachiopoda sp.	2					2
Bryozoa sp.	2			1		3

Pycnogonida sp.			1			1
Xenophyophoroidea			1			1
Ziphiidae sp.	2		1	1		4
Zoarcidae sp.				1		1
Unknown Taxa		1				1
cf. Cnidaria sp.		1				1
TOTAL	34	38	16	25	46	159

Figure 4. Example specimens (non-cephalopod) from expedition

Transects and video annotation

Approximately 141 hours of video imagery was collected on the expedition (Table 8). At the beginning of the cruise, there were some issues with video file export that are still being resolved by SOI, as noted below. This imagery was ingested into the Tator annotation platform during the expedition (Figure 5); the science party will continue to work with the video imagery after the cruise to use annotations for biogeographic and behavior studies and creation of Biodiversity Atlas of the area.

Twenty-three video transects were collected on the expedition: 5 at El Dorado, 5 at Caballito, 5 at Fuente, 4 at Tengosed, and 4 at La Pulpería. The transects varied from 40-110 meters in length. Most transects were collected over rocky seafloor on the outcrops, but some transects at the base of Caballito and on top of Fuente were over sedimented seafloor. Transects were primarily conducted at ROV transit speeds of 0.2 m/s, 1-2 m above bottom, with 10-cm lasers on, and with the science camera set to no zoom and tilted just above the ROV tool tray.

Table 8. List of video files from Fkt231202 available in Tator

Dive	# of video files	Hours of video	Notes
619	23	3.7	Missing several video files - gap between 2023-12-04T18:35:27.mp4 and 2023-12-04T21:06:11. Also missing videos from the ascent.
620	34	14.2	Missing video files at the beginning of the dive. Clips start with 2023-12-05T12:38;15.mp4 at 1793m water depth
621	12	5.2	Missing video clips from the descent. Clips start with 2023-12-06T12:55:06.mp4 at 1981 m depth.
622	16	7.5	none
623	0	0	Dive aborted
624	33	16.0	none
625	28	13.5	none
626	39	17	none
627	39	14.8	none
628	32	15.1	none
629	27	12.4	none
630	21	9.9	none
631	26	11.8	none
TOTAL	330	141.1	

Figure 5. Example of animal localizations annotated on Tator platform.

Octopus specimen collection and microbiome sampling

Methods: For specimens of *Muusoctopus* and *Graneledone*, a tissue sample of arm muscle was taken from each specimen and preserved in ethanol 95%. The microbiome samples from *Muusoctopus* were divided in two parts; half was preserved in formalin 10% and half in Zymo DNA/RNA shield. The bulk of the specimens were fixed in formalin 10% and will be accessioned into the collections of the Museum of Zoology at the University of Costa Rica. The eggs were preserved in ethanol 95%. For *Vitreledonella*, the whole specimen was preserved in ethanol 95%, and tissue samples were taken and preserved in ethanol 95% as well.

Sample summary: Thirteen specimens of benthic octopods and one midwater octopus were collected (Tables 9 and 10). There are at least four distinct species, all of which are undescribed, represented by specimens from this small area visited during Fkt231202 (Figure 6). One species is not represented by a physical specimen but is well documented by photos (Figure 7). Nine specimens of the species that associates with hydrothermal fluid flow, *Muusoctopus* type 1, were dissected for microbiome research.

Observations: Most octopods observed at El Dorado Hill were female. The few males were not observed interacting with females. Females rarely displaced others from apparently preferred niches, jostling each other arm-to-arm, until one left the immediate area. Most females remained immobile in the “brooding position”, with their arms reflexed aborally. The eggs observed were early stage, being glossy and smooth usually without immediately sign of embryonic development. However, recovery of some of these eggs revealed small embryos inside. No fully senescent females or fully developed embryos were observed, but occasionally senescent males were seen away from areas of fluid flow. However, at least two apparently fully developed hatchlings, without any sign of yolk sacs, swam across ROV SuBastian’s field of view. The population thus sustains all phases of embryonic development, allowing successful reproduction. The artificial shelters (clay pots and PVC pipes) were largely devoid of octopods. One individual, a non-brooding female) was found in one PVC pipe which had been placed in fluid flow.

Table 9. Summary of cephalopod samples by dive.

Asterisks indicate potential type specimens.

Dive	Site name	Sample ID	SpeciesID	Sex	Microbiome Sampling
619	El Dorado Hill	018	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	Male	yes
619	El Dorado Hill	026	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	Female	yes
620	La Pulpería Hill	050	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	Female	yes
620	La Pulpería Hill	052	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	eggs	yes
621	Tengosed Seamount	080	Glass octopus <i>Vitreledonella</i>	?	no
622	Tengosed Seamount	096	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 3*	Female	no
622	Tengosed Seamount	097	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 3*	eggs	no
624	El Dorado Hill	145	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	Female from trap	yes
626	El Dorado Hill	192	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	eggs	yes
626	El Dorado Hill	193	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	female	yes
627	Caballito Knoll	200	<i>Graneledone</i> sp.*	male	no
628	La Pulpería Hill	217	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	female	yes
628	La Pulpería Hill	218	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	eggs	yes
631	Fuente Knoll	306	<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 3 or 4*	male	no

Table 9. Summary of cephalopod samples by site and species.

Species	Dorado	La Pulpería	Tengosed	Caballito	Fuente	Total
<i>Graneledone</i> sp.	0	0	0	1	0	1
<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 1	5 (4A/1E)	4 (2A/2E)	0	0	0	9
<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 3	0	0	2 (1A/1E)	0	0	2
<i>Muusoctopus</i> sp. Type 4	0	0	0	0	1	1
<i>Vitreledonella</i> cf. <i>richardi</i>	0	0	1	0	0	1
TOTAL	5	4	3	1	1	14

A: Adult, E: eggs

Figure 6. Photographs of cephalopod specimens

Figure 6A

Muusoctopus sp. Type 1 male from 619

Figure 6B

Muusoctopus sp. Type 3 from 622

Figure 6C.

Male *Graneledone* on Caballito from 627

Figure 6D.

Male *Muusoctopus*, either Type 3 or potentially new Type 4, from Fuente dive 631

Figure 6E. Octopus embryo inside egg

Figure 7. In situ photograph of potential new *Graneledone* species which could not be collected.

Coral Challenge Experiments

Eight coral specimens were samples for challenge experiments to examine respiration activity of live/dead corals and their microbiomes as compared to two background bottom seawater (Table 10). Upon arrival of the ROV on deck, corals were photographed for taxonomic purposes as per the general protocol for all specimens brought on board. Small coral fragments were then placed into microrespirometry chambers in a controlled laboratory environment to measure basal metabolic rate in comparison to various challenge treatments. Challenges focused on various nutrients including nutrient broth (Luria broth, a common microbial growth media), marine media, and various components of each including yeast extract, tryptone, sterile seawater from surface waters, from deep waters and filtered instant ocean seawater. Corals were also challenged with a standard lab-grown BSL1 bacteria culture of *E. Coli*, prepped and grown at the Universidad de Costa Rica, treated with and without co-Amoxiclav antibiotics. Oxygen consumption of corals was recorded in real time with the microrespirometer, and revealed that some corals animals and/or their associated microbial communities responded to dissolved nutrients in seawater. Further analysis is required to determine strength and mechanism of response, but these results provide an important first glimpse into deep-sea coral ecology and physiology, opening up ideas about alternatives to heterotrophy as a means for nutrient access. To that end, follow-up analyses with stable isotopes, %C and %N content, and transcriptomics will help us confirm the uptake (or not) of various nutrients. Understanding deepwater coral physiology and ecology is a nascent science that can help provide the context for various management and conservation actions in terms of management plan development, structure, and potential for success.

Table 10. Samples used for coral challenge experiments

Sample ID	Dive	Taxonomic Family	Tentative species or description
019	619	Primnoidae	Thourella sp.
057	620	Primnoidae	Narella sp.
076	621	Primnoidae	Narella sp.
095*	622	Chrysogorgiidae	Chrysogorgiidae. sp.
138A-D	624	Primnoidae	Thourella sp.
245	629	Primnoidae	Calyptrophora sp.
250	629	Primnoidae	Narella sp.
309-310	630	Chrysogorgiidae	Chrysogorgiidae. sp.
199	627	n.a.	Background seawater
259	629	n.a.	Background seawater

* specimen was no longer viable prior to experiment so did not contribute to results

Rock Sample summary

General description: Basalts are the rocks that form the basement of the seamounts, covered by laminated calcareous ooze. The thickness of the ooze was measured in some escarpments, such as Tengosed (14 m) and Fuente (11 m). A top black layer in several of the seamounts is observed. The layer consists of a siltstone covered by a crust of polymetallic oxides aggregates, in some parts nodules can be observed above the seamount structure

Methods for microbiological sampling of rocks: Briefly, manganese oxide-encrusted rock samples are collected from the ROV Biobox using gloves and immediately placed in a bucket of chilled 0.2- μm filter-sterilized seawater with enough volume for full submersion. The sample is subsequently photographed and placed in a EtOH-sterilized rock crushing box where smaller segments (<4cc) are chipped off using a sterile chisel. The smaller segments are transferred to a sterile metal mortar and pestle where they are further pulverized to ~500 μm size coarse powder. 30-50 cc of this material is placed in a 50cc falcon tube and immediately placed at -80C

for DNA extraction. To preserve samples for cell counts, 2 cc of pulverized rock are placed in two separate 2 ml microcentrifuge and submerged in 0.2- μ m filter sterilized 4% paraformaldehyde diluted in PBS and stored cold. Also, 2-5 cc of pulverized sample is carefully wrapped in a square aluminum foil cutout and, taking care to ensure the rock sample never touches the plastic, placed in a 50 cc falcon tube for TOC analysis and stored at -30C. A variation of this sampling method was used for manganese-oxide encrusted beaked whale fossils, where the manganese oxide crust was scraped off with sterile tools. The remaining residual intact rock sample is left to dry and along with any remaining crushed samples for archive at the USGS (for mineral crust composition analysis) and the Central America School of Geology at Universidad de Costa Rica.

Sample summary: Twenty-three rock samples were collected; ten of these rock samples were sampled for microbiological analysis (Tables 11 and 12). *Note that some of the samples were logged as Biology or Sediment samples in the Master Sample Log.*

Table 11. Rock sample descriptions

Site	Dive	# of rock samples (description - BOLD = MBIO samples)
El Dorado Hill	619	-007 Basalt underneath the 23 Ma microbe trap set
La Pulpería Hill	620	-035 rock underneath the 23 Ma microbe trap set. Encrusted mudstone with worm tubes on the surface. -048 rock with hydrozoan -054 rock -055 rock with octocoral & cirripedia -056 rock with byozoan and brittle star -060 rock with euplectellid sponge and shrimp
Tengosed Seamount	621	-072 rock next to Marker X vent site. Thin crust over siltstone. -075 calcareous ooze
Tengosed Seamount	622	-089 Rock from Skate Park. Crusted mudstone.
El Dorado Hill	624	-109 Nodule from "lobate lava" field on flank of outcrop. -123 rock for microbiology?
Caballito Knoll	625	-165 beaked whale fossil
El Dorado Hill	626	-194 Rock from Marker R for imagery analysis
La Pulpería Hill	628	-209 Escarpment siltstone -210 Scoop of calcareous wall -212 beaked whale fossil -227 Rock from Marker Q vent site

Tengosed Seamount	629	-242 Rock with octocorals
El Dorado Hill	630	-275 Rock from Marker A
Fuente Knoll	631	-297 Rock crust over Miocene sediment -303 altered pillow -311 beaked whale fossil

Table 12. Photos of rock samples

Sample	In situ	Lab
007		
035		

048

0 3 cm

054

HEADING	161
O2 CON.	138 μ M
O2 SAT.	33.8%
DEPTH	2820 m
SALINITY	35.2 PSU
TEMP.	1.81 °C

2023-12-05 21:37:39 UTC

0 3 cm

<p>055</p>		
<p>056</p>		
<p>060</p>		

<p>072</p>		
<p>075</p>		

089	<p>0 3 cm</p>	
109	<p>0 3 cm</p>	
123	<p>0 3 cm</p>	

165		
194		
209		

<p>211</p>	<p>0 3 cm</p>	
<p>212</p>		
<p>227</p>	<p>0 3 cm</p>	

<p>242</p>	<p>0 3 cm</p>	
<p>275</p>	<p>0 3 cm</p>	
<p>297</p>	<p>0 3 cm</p>	

<p>303</p>	<p>0 3 cm</p>	
<p>311</p>		

Sediment Sample summary

Samples: Four sediment sampling events occurred at four different sites, collecting a total of 22 cores (Table 13). Two sets of push cores were collected in between Caballito Knoll and La Pulperia Hill. The push core sample set from Tengosed Seamount sampled a 14m tall escarpment, with cores taken horizontally from the face (and one collected vertically in modern sediment at the base, sample 241). Samples 238, 240, and 239 came from the top, middle, and bottom of the escarpment, respectively. The push core sample set from Fuente Knoll sampled a 11m tall escarpment, with cores taken horizontally from the face (and one collected vertically in modern sediment at the base, 299). Samples 294, 295, and 296 came from the top, middle, and bottom of the escarpment, respectively. These collections were subsampled for a wide variety of analyses, including description of sediment fungi and worms (by shore-based collaborator Keiler Rojas, UCR), description of sediment protists and meiofauna, sediment physical description via smear slides (by Maria Sandoval), description of sediment porewater geochemistry (by Geoff Wheat) and microbial community taxonomic and functional diversity with ‘omics based approaches (by Gustavo Ramirez).

Table 13. Overview of sediment push cores collected for various analyses, with sample numbers for various analyses.

Dive	Location	# cores	DNA/ Geochem	Fungi / Worms / Genetics	Plastic	Geol	Biostrat.
625	Caballito Knoll	8	156, 171	155	158	154, 168, 157	168
627	Caballito-La Pulperia	6	203	(203, 202) 205	204	206, 207, 202	-
629	Tengosed Seamount	4	(238, 239, 240)	-	-	238, 239, 240, 241	-
631	Fuente Knoll	4	(294, 295, 296, 299)	-	-	294, 295, 296, 299	-

In situ dissolved oxygen and temperature measurements

Methods: The Aanderaa dissolved oxygen (DO) sensor was attached to an electrical whip and placed into a holder with a tee handle for ROV manipulation. The ROV pilots added a length of whip which was cut at the end of the expedition; thus the 4 wires are no longer exposed but embedded in the epoxy connector. This sensor was deployed on each of the dives except for the last dive. Data were incorporated into the ROV data network and provided as a txt file. During deployment the intake was positioned within a crack until a minimum DO was reached.

Observations:

The science party employed three methods for making in situ measurements of dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature: (1) use of a third-party Aanderaa dissolved oxygen probe integrated into the ROV electronics and mounted on a wand, (2) use of a third-party autonomous RBR DO sensor with temperature sensor, and (3) use of the ROV SuBastian high-temperature probe (Table 14).

Though recording data throughout all dives but the last one, thus providing records of bottom water temperature and DO, the Aanderaa probe was intentionally used eight times to record formation fluid conditions at hydrothermal springs. Formation fluids at El Dorado Hill had DO minimums of 55.8 μ M, 57.5 μ M, and 109.1 μ M at Markers R, K, and A, respectively, with temperature maximums of 12.15 $^{\circ}$ C, 11.71 $^{\circ}$ C, and 2.3 $^{\circ}$ C. Three measurements at Marker Q on La Pulpería Hill were 83.7, 88.6, and 109.5 μ M DO with temperatures of 2.24-4.95 $^{\circ}$ C. One measurement of the Marker X vent site at Tengosed on Dive 621 recorded a minimum DO of 92.1 μ M and maximum temperature of 2.47 $^{\circ}$ C. A second attempt on Dive 629 was not successful due to difficulty getting the sensor into the flow.

The RBR autonomous DO and temperature sensor was deployed twice. The first deployment occurred on Dive 620 on La Pulpería outcrop. The sampler recorded DO and temperature every 30 minutes and was deployed such that the oxygen sensor was touching the Fast Flow OsmoSampler intake (Marker Q). The logger was recovered on Dive 628 and the data were downloaded. Data reveal a maximum temperature of 4.1 $^{\circ}$ C and a minimum DO of 94.5 μ M. Both differ as a function of tidal cycles.

The second deployment occurred on Dive 629 to Tengosed Seamount (Marker X). The sampler was lowered into the hole from which crustal fluids discharge and collected data (2 minute interval) for ~12 minutes. The sensor was recovered on this dive revealing a maximum temperature of 3.13 $^{\circ}$ C and a minimum DO of 79.5 μ M in the hole

Table 14. Summary of dissolved oxygen and temperature on Fkt231202

Site	Dive	Event info (RBR indicates autonomous sensor)	BW temp. ($^{\circ}$ C)	BW DO (μ M)	Spring temp. ($^{\circ}$ C)	Spring DO (μ M)
Dorado	619	1 - Marker K	1.87	111.5	11.71	57.5
La Pulperia	620	1 - Marker Q	1.90	112.2	4.35	88.6
La Pulpería	620	2 - Marker Q	1.90	112.2	4.95	83.7

Tengosed	621	1 - Marker X	2.39	92.4	2.47	92.1
Tengosed	622	No events	2.44	88.6	n.a.	n.a.
Dorado	624	1 - Marker R	1.9	110.7	12.15	55.84
Caballito	625	No events	1.9	112	n.a.	n.a.
Dorado	626	No events	1.9	110	n.a.	n.a.
La Pulpería	628	1 - Marker Q	1.9	110.9	2.24	109.5
La Pulpería	628	2 - Marker Q	1.9	110.7	2.29	109
La Pulpería	628	RBR - Marker Q	1.82	110.5	4.1	94.5
Tengosed	629	RBR - Marker X	2.24	90.04	3.13	79.5
Dorado	630	1 - Marker A	1.0	110	2.3	109.1

Figure 8. Plot of dissolved oxygen versus temperature.

Data for bottom water and hydrothermal spring formation fluids at the three vent sites in La Pampa Submarina, showing three different trends.

Deployments & Recoveries summary

OsmoSamplers

Recoveries: Two Standard OsmoSamplers were recovered that were deployed during the Flt230602 expedition in June 2023. One was recovered on Dive 619 from the Marker K/W area on El Dorado Hill. Here the maximum temperature was ~12°C and the dissolved oxygen reached ~56 µmol/kg. The second OsmoSampler was recovered during Dive 620 on La Pulpería Hill. Both OsmoSamplers had single 8-membrane osmotic pumps and a 300-m-long spool of Teflon tubing. Upon recovery both were removed from the milk crate. The salinity in the freshwater reservoir of each was 0 per mil. The sampler from El Dorado reached 0 per ml salinity at sample 80; each sample was 1.2 m in length. Similarly, the sampler at La Pulpería outcrop reached 0 per mil salinity at sample number 100. Both systems functioned as expected.

New deployments: Two Fast-Flow OsmoSamplers were deployed and recovered during the expedition. Both OsmoSamplers included two pumps and two coils of ~150 m of small-bore Teflon tubing. The reason for the redundancy was to try two different membranes. One pump used a cellulose acetate (CA) membrane and the other used a ACM3 PA RO triSep membrane. Both worked on the bench and pumped about 40 ml in a 12-hour period the night before the deployment. One was deployed on La Pulpería outcrop (Dive 620) where water samples were collected (Marker Q). The other was deployed on Tanged Seamount in the hole that was discovered during the previous expedition (Marker X). Both deployments included a temperature logger at the intake (La Pulpería - Temp SN 768600; Tanged - Temp SN 768604). Both were recovered (Dives 628 and 629) and water was extracted from the Teflon tubing. Each of the four Fast Flow pumps over pumped, resulting in salty water in the freshwater reservoir of the pump. Chemical analysis of the reservoir fluid will be conducted to assess how much the pumps oversampled to provide a timeline for each sample. No chemical analyses were conducted at sea.

Microbe Colonization Experiments (aka Microbe Traps)

Overview: All five microbial colonization experiments deployed on the Fkt230602 expedition were recovered on expedition Fkt231202 (Figure 9, Table 15). Four of these were at El Dorado Hill: two at the Marker K/R/W region with the most vigorous flow, one at Marker A, and one on the flank with no evidence of venting. The fifth experiment set was at La Pulpería at Marker Q.

Methods: Trap disassembly starts by separating PVC sleeves from dive weights by clipping off zip ties. Each PVC sleeve unit is placed on a sterile petri-plate surface. Using a flamed-sterilized cutter knife, the top mesh cover is cut off around the inner diameter of the PCV housing. This provides access to the substrate wrapped in sterile cooking mesh within the housing chamber holding the colonization substrates. The mesh wrap is opened by cutting a small zip tie used to fasten it. When exposed, the substrate in the mesh is lifted above the petri plate (held by the mesh bag) and rinsed by slowly pouring 20-40 mls of pre-chilled (5°C) 0.2-µm-sterilized

seawater through the sample. The rinse collects on the petri plate surface below it. The substrate, still contained in the mesh, is placed in a new dry sterile petri plate surface. Using a flame sterilized scoop, rinsed substrates are transferred to labeled 50 ml falcon tubes which are subsequently stored at -80°C. All accessory components (e.g.: zip ties, PVC housing, bag and housing wall mesh) for each deployment substrate are placed in individual sterile bags and stored at -80°C labeled with appropriate sample numbers.

Table 15. Overview of Microbial Colonization Experiment recoveries

Dive	Location	Sample #	Comparison Rock Sample #
619	El Dorado Hill - Marker W (Figure 10)	002-006	007
620	La Pulpería Hill - Marker Q (Figure 11)	030-034	035
624	El Dorado Hill - flank (Figure 12)	104-108	109
624	El Dorado Hill - Marker R (Figure 13 and 14)	117-121	123
630	El Dorado Hill - Marker A (Figure 15)	270-274	275

Figure 9. Overview of locations of Octopus Odyssey microbe trap experiments.

Figure 10. Microbe traps recovered from Marker W on El Dorado Hill

A. Microbial colonization experiments at marker W site; B. Rhodochrosite (blue, sample 003); C. Fresh Basalt (purple, sample 004); D. Mild Steel (orange, sample 005); E. Glass Wool (green, sample 002); F. "Rust patch" on Glass Wool dive weight; G. 23 Mya Basalt (red, sample 006); H. Native Rock (sample 007) located directly below the 23 Mya basalt trap.

Figure 11. Microbe traps recovered from Marker Q on La Pulpería Hill

A. Microbial colonization experiments at marker Q site; B. Glass Wool (030); C. Fresh Basalt (031); D. Rhodochrosite (032); E. 23 Mya Basalt (033); F. Mild Steel close up (034); G. Native Rock Collection (035); H. Native Rock close up (035).

Fkt231202; Dive: 620: **La Pulpería Seamount.**

Figure 12. Microbe traps recovered from the flank of on El Dorado Hill

A) Microbial colonization experiments at a lobate lava field West of Dorado Hill; B) Deployment site temperature measurements. C) Mild Steel (**104**); D) Rhodochrosite (**106**); E) Fresh Basalt (**107**); F) Glass Wool (**108**); G) 23 Mya Native Basalt (**105**); H) Lobate Lava rock collection for molecular biology (**109**).

Fkt231202: Dive 623: **Lobate lava field west of Dorado Outcrop**

Figure 13. Microbe traps recovered from Marker R on El Dorado Hill

A) Microbial colonization experiments location undergoing temperature measurement, Marker R in El Dorado Outcrop; B) Glass Wool (121). C) Mild Steel (117); D) 23 Mya Native Basalt (120); E) Fresh Basalt (119); F) Rhodochrosite(118).

Figure 14. Octopus egg cement on Sample 120 Microbe Trap

Additional Notes on sample **120**. This microbial trap, containing 23 Mya Dorado Native Basalt, had a layer of green octopus clutch cement with approximately 25 eggs stalks but no embryos.

Figure 15. Microbe traps recovered from Marker A on El Dorado Hill

A) Microbial colonization experiments at Marker A in North El Dorado Hill. Each color-coded substrate type was assigned the following sample numbers: Mild Steel (**270, orange**); Rhodochrosite (**274, blue**); Fresh Basalt (**273, purple**); Glass Wool (**271, green**); 23 Mya Native Basalt (**272, red**). B) Close up the Mild Steel (**270**) colonization chamber collection. C) Placing of experiment in Bio Biox-A in the forward payload area of ROV Subastian.

Fkt231202_Dive630. El Dorado Hill

Multibeam summary

Multibeam bathymetric data were collected during FKt231202 with a Kongsberg EM124 system, resulting in 7416 km² of new data. Data were generally acquired whenever the ship transited between worksites, using track lines set by the Marine Technicians, resulting in repeat coverage of key features and the surrounding areas. Targeted acquisition of new data was focused on the NE side of Fuente Knoll and the SW side of Caballito Knoll, to fill in gaps in high resolution data, with track lines recommended by the science party. Data from this expedition were merged with some data collected during FKt230602 and prior expeditions (AT26-09 and AT26-24) to create a composite bathymetric coverage of the study region. The EM124 system acquires data at 12 KHz and merges ship position information to generate relatively high-resolution, swath maps in real time. After initial processing with Kongsberg software, data were brought into Fleidermaus 7 for filtering and additional adjustment. Final grid files were output with a resolution of ~10 m, and exported in georeferenced TIF format for use with mapping systems.

Figure 16. Composite display of bathymetric maps from both expeditions

Figure 17. Bathymetric map of El Dorado Hill.

Note that this map uses 1m-resolution bathymetric data from AT26-09 expedition, not including new data from Octopus Odyssey expeditions.

Figure 18. Bathymetric map of Tengosed Seamount.

Figure 19. Bathymetric map of Caballito Knoll and La Pulperia Hill.

Figure 20. Bathymetric map of Fuente Knoll and Mambo Kita Hill

Heat Flow summary

Methods: Heat flow was determined using a 66-cm long, *Alvin*-style heat flow probe. Two probes were fielded for expeditions FKt230602, both constructed in 1996, with serial numbers 9 and 10. Each tool has five thermistor sensors separated by 15 cm, inside a titanium lance with a radius of 0.49 cm, and a circuit board in a pressure case with controller, A/D converter, and communications components. There is a heater wire in the sensor tube that releases a controlled heat pulse for determination of thermal conductivity. There is no separate bottom-water sensor. The tools are operated with power provided by the submersible through an underwater cable and connectors, and controlled using a Java program that sends commands, receives data and writes it to a file, and displays data graphically to assess station progress. The ROV SuBastian has a mounting system on the starboard side with a vertical guide rail and a hydraulic ram that is used to insert the lance into the seafloor. A typical measurement during our expedition began with settling the ROV on the seafloor and inserting a test probe into the sediment with a manipulator, to verify that the sediment was sufficiently deep and soft. The test probe was left in the seafloor and was held by a manipulator to aid with stabilizing the vehicle. Propulsion was reduced, or ideally turned off, to minimize ROV motion that could impart undesired frictional heating during the measurement. Communication with heat flow probe was established, measurements were made every 2 sec, and 30-60 s of bottom water data was acquired to check on probe performance and to provide a bottom water calibration. When ready, the hydraulic ram was advanced to insert the probe into the seafloor, ideally in a single, rapid motion that places all five sensors in the sediment, and the probe is held stationary for the desired time. For a normal measurement, the friction associated with probe insertion would be allowed to dissipate for ~7-8 minutes, and a calibrated heat pulse would be released and allowed to dissipate for another ~7-8 minutes. Once a measurement is completed, the probe is pulled from the seafloor, recording of data is stopped, and the data file is closed. Processing is normally accomplished with software that calibrates and corrects each of the sensors, using bottom water as a reference, and temperatures are extrapolated to estimate equilibrium values if the tool were allowed to equilibrate fully, with adjustment to thermal properties as indicated by the response to the heat pulse. Processing steps are based on an approach developed in the 1980s and subsequently updated to include an estimate of measurement uncertainty (e.g., Villinger and Davis, 1987; Stein and Fisher, 2001). Unfortunately, the heat flow probes available for FKt231202 were found to be electrically unstable. Tool 9 worked well initially on the bench, but generated ground faults when connected to the ROV. The pressure case for this tool's electronics was opened, and 10-15 mL of water

was found inside. The circuit board had been damaged by exposure to water. It is suspected that a leak developed due to aging of one or both o-rings sealing the case, as we could see no other evidence of damage or failure that would have allowed a leak. Tool 10 did not give ground faults and its electronics appeared to be undamaged, but its readings were consistently ~ 3 °C too high, and data also showed evidence for drift and noise, including variations of ± 0.01 deg between sequential measurements, and occasional offsets of up to 0.5 °C. It was noted that the apparent differences between sensors remained mostly constant and were consistent with offsets observed when the same tool was used successfully in 2013. For this reason, tool 10 was used for all thermal data collected as part of the heat flow program on FKt231202.

Measurements: Fourteen heat flow measurements were made (Table 16, Figure 21), all in the area between and on Cabillito and La Pulpería outcrops. This area was the highest priority for new heat flow data during FKt231202 to help assess if recharge through Cabillito outcrop could be the source of water discharging at La Pulpería, which supports the associated seafloor ecosystem. Measurements were made during two ROV dives, 625 and 627.

We found that the electronic noise described earlier prevented use of standard processing techniques for interpretation of heat flow data. Instead we took the following approach. Subseafloor data were corrected by subtracting values measured with the shallowest sensor (T5), which was positioned for most measurements to be just above the seafloor, and therefore measures bottom water during the insertion. This approach helped to correct for electronic noise, which was generally consistent for all the sensor channels. However, this approach also meant that we were not able to make use of the heat pulse for determining thermal conductivity of the sediment. Earlier studies showed that thermal conductivity in the upper 0.6 m of sediment was generally ~ 0.8 W/m-K, so this value was combined with measured thermal gradients to provide an initial estimate of heat flow. A custom code was made to subtract T5 temperature values from data collected with other sensors, display the results, and aid with estimation of equilibrium values. We did not fire a heat pulse after initial measurements on dive 625, instead leaving the probe in the seafloor for 10-12 minutes, so that final values could be interpreted as roughly representative of equilibrium values. The sensors below T5 were not all placed below the seafloor during all measurements, as the pitch and roll of the ROV determined the final positioning of the tool when the hydraulic ram was fully extended, and the deepest sensor (T1) was also found to drift relative to readings from other sensors during some measurements. Thus interpretations were based mainly on responses of sensors T2, T3, and T4, with corrections applied using data from T5 (Figure 22).

In general, heat flow values were found to be low (~ 20 -50 mW/m²) on the flat seafloor between the two outcrops, with higher values determined on the edge of Cabillito and La Pulpería outcrops (> 100 mW/m²). Values determined between the outcrops were all well below lithospheric for ~ 18 -24 M.y. old seafloor, 100-120 mW/m². This is consistent with the area surveyed being on the "cool" side of the thermal transition associated with the presence of seamounts and other outcrops. Low values on the flat seafloor close to Cabillito outcrop, and somewhat elevated on the edge of La Pulpería outcrop, are consistent with flow from Cabillito to La Pulpería, although the pattern is not as extreme as seen between Tengosed and Dorado outcrops. The discharge from La Pulpería may be weaker than that from Dorado, but it is hard to be sure of this since surveys are incomplete, flow rates can change with time (and tides), and discharge temperatures from La Pulpería appear to be lower than from Dorado.

Table 16. Summary of heat flow measurements.

ID	Latitude ^a (°N)	Longitude ^a (°E)	File Start	File End	HP ^a	Estimated gradient (°C/m)	Estimated heat flow (mW/m ²)
HF-625-01	8.63747	-87.33151	12/8/23 13:43	12/8/23 14:01	Y	0.055	44
HF-625-02 ^b	8.63602	-87.33263	12/8/23 14:47	12/8/23 15:03	Y	0.024	19
HF-625-03 ^c	8.63223	-87.33509	12/8/23 15:50	12/8/23 16:07	Y	0.100	80
HF-627-01	8.61997	-87.31505	12/10/23 14:27	12/10/23 14:37	N	0.035	28
HF-627-02	8.62103	-87.31308	12/10/23 15:09	12/10/23 15:27	N	0.030	24
HF-627-03	8.62202	-87.31111	12/10/23 15:53	12/10/23 16:12	N	0.059	47
HF-627-04	8.62347	-87.30810	12/10/23 16:40	12/10/23 17:01	N	0.047	38
HF-627-05	8.62501	-87.30505	12/10/23 17:30	12/10/23 17:51	N	0.028	23
HF-627-06	8.62597	-87.30311	12/10/23 18:23	12/10/23 18:40	N	0.023	18
HF-627-07	8.62703	-87.30115	12/10/23 19:07	12/10/23 19:27	N	0.060	48
HF-627-08	8.62799	-87.29908	12/10/23 19:50	12/10/23 20:10	N	0.064	51
HF-627-09	8.62921	-87.29673	12/10/23 20:35	12/10/23 20:54	N	0.044	35
HF-627-10	8.63047	-87.29433	12/10/23 21:25	12/10/23 21:43	N	0.053	42
HF-627-11	8.63160	-87.29221	12/10/23 22:08	12/10/23 22:29	N	0.087	69

^aHP indicates if a heat pulse was fired, but no heat pulse data were used to determine thermal conductivity. Thermal gradient was calculated from least-squares best-fitting straight line through equilibrium subseafloor data. Heat flow values were calculated assuming thermal conductivity of 0.8 W/m-K.

^b HF-625-02 was intended to be co-located with HF-540-01, made during Fkt230602.

^c HF-625-03 was intended to be co-located with HF-540-06, made during Fkt230602

Figure 21. Map of heat flow locations

Data from FKt230602 are shown with diamonds (HF-539 and HF-540), and data from FKt231202 (this expedition, HF-625 and HF-627) are shown with four-pointed stars.

Figure 22. Example of heat flow data from Fkt231202,

From Station HF-627-05 Clockwise from the top left: (1) Raw data, showing elevated and unstable temperature readings. (2) Section of data from before penetration, after subtraction of measurements made with T5 (top sensor), showing consistency of temperature differences between sensor pairs. (3) Final inferred equilibrium temperatures, with best-fitting line through data from T2, T3, and T4. (4) Apparent thermal gradients between sensor pairs. (5) Cleaned data after subtracting values from T5 measured throughout the penetration. Box at end of record shows values averaged to estimate in-situ equilibrium temperatures. This is one of the "cleanest" records from the transect run on dive 627.

Temperature Logger Summary

Methods: Five (5) autonomous temperature loggers were deployed during FKt230602 and recovered during FKt231202. These were Onset (brand) model U12 loggers having a titanium pressure case, a temperature range of -40 to 125 °C, resolution of ~0.02°C (12 bit A/D), and memory capable of storing ~43,000 values. The loggers were programmed for sampling at 30-minute intervals and deployed inside hollow T-handles, with the sensor end of the logger exposed. All loggers were deployed adjacent to seafloor markers, and three of them had an additional "ROVit" donut float attached (Table 17).

Measurements: Data were downloaded when loggers were recovered, then plotted to assess dynamic behavior (Figures 23-27). In general, variations in temperature tend to be associated with twice-daily tides, and likely result from variations in: (a) discharge rate, (b) bottom currents, and/or (c) flow of bottom water through outcrops. Lower discharge rates are expected to be associated with lower peak temperatures because rising fluids lose more heat during ascent and/or there is greater mixing between hydrothermal (formation) fluids and bottom water. Loggers were deployed with sensors pushed as far as possible into flowing springs, but it was difficult in some cases to set the probes deep enough to avoid mixing with bottom water. Two loggers were redeployed for 5-6 days during FKt231202 adjacent to the intakes of "fast-flow" OsmoSamplers (Table 18). One of these was deployed on La Pulpería hill and the other at Tengosed seamount, both sampling at 30 minute intervals (Figure 28).

Table 17. Six-month temperature logger deployments

Logger S/N	Marker ^a	ROVit ^a	Lat (°N)	Long (°E)	Start ^b	Stop ^b
768601	X (Tengosed)	–	9.12066	-86.94358	06/01/23 21:17:16	12/06/23 18:17:16
768602	A (Dorado)	C	9.08872	-87.10168	06/01/23 21:15:00	12/13/23 13:15:00
768600	W (Dorado)	A	9.08250	-87.09541	06/01/23 09:13:47	12/05/23 05:43:47
768604	Q (La Pulpería)	–	8.62120	-87.27877	06/01/23 21:12:00	12/06/23 03:12:00
768616	R (Dorado)	B	9.08255	-87.09543	06/01/23 20:41:35	12/08/23 16:11:35

^a Site markers on square floats, refer to surrounding area. ROVit labels were placed on small "donut" floats attached to some of the T-handles used to deploy individual thermal loggers.

^b First and last records in data files. All dates/times are UTC; times logged using AM/PM nomenclature, shown in table using 24-hour nomenclature. Logging interval for instruments was 30 min.

Table 18. Short-term (days) temperature logger deployments

Logger S/N	Marker ^a	ROVit ^a	Lat (°N)	Long (°E)	Start ^b	Stop ^b
768600	Q (La Pulpería)	A	8.62175	-87.27963	12/5/23 01:00:00	12/12/23 08:00:00
768604	X (Tengosed)	W	9.12066	-86.94358	12/6/23 05:00:00	12/12/23 15:00:00

^a Site markers on square floats, refer to surrounding area. ROVit labels were placed on small

^b First and last records in data files. All dates/times are UTC; times logged using AM/PM nomenclature, shown in table using 24-hour nomenclature. Logging interval for instruments was 30 min.

Figure 23. Six-month temperature record from Marker W at El Dorado Hill.

Lower plot shows 30-day interval marked with box in upper panel. Note relatively continuous variability between 8-10°C at peak and 2-5°C at minimum, showing clear tidal influence.

Figure 24. Six-month temperature record from Marker R at El Dorado Hill.

Lower plot shows 30-day interval marked with box in upper panel. Note relatively continuous variability between 10-12°C or 4-6°C and minimum daily temperatures of ~2-3°C throughout, again showing clear tidal influence.

Figure 25. Six-month temperature record from Marker A at El Dorado Hill.

Lower plot shows 30-day interval marked with box in upper panel. This record shows a relatively extreme range in temperature, with many varied values consistent with bottom water, indicating that this spring is highly intermittent, as visually observed during the dive.

Figure 26. Six-month temperature record from Marker Q at La Pulpería Hill. Lower plot shows 30-day interval marked with box in upper panel. This record shows variability at multiple timescales, with peak temperatures of ~5-7 °C and minimum daily temperatures of ~2-4 °C.

Figure 27. Six-month temperature record from Marker X at Tengosed Seamount.

Lower plot shows 30-day interval marked with box in upper panel. This record shows daily peak temperatures near 3.1 °C, and minimum daily temperatures of ~2.2-2.9 °C.

Figure 28. Short-term temperature records at two hydrothermal springs.

Upper panel are data from Marker Q at La Pulpería Hill and lower panel are data from Marker X at Tengosed Seamount.

SUPR fluid sampling summary

Methods: Hydrothermal spring fluids and background seawater samples were collected to determine linkages between fluid-rock alteration, microbial processes, and animals at seafloor outcrops, including key ecosystem services in these underexplored deep-sea habitats. Samples were collected using the SUPR Sampler, an in situ pumping and filtration system consisting of a 14 port double through valve and a pumping system with a digital flowmeter (Figure 29). The intake is equipped with an integrated temperature sensor as well. The SUPR can collect multiple sample types: filtered material, whole water, and filtered water. This is done by configuring the base SUPR valve and pumping system with 14 different sampling devices (i.e. filters and water bottles). For this cruise, the SUPR was set up with 4 filters (2-0.2 μM PES and 2-GF/75-0.3 μM) for concentrating microbial biomass on the seafloor. The filter holders used include a ~20 mL reservoir for RNALater, enabling fixation of the filter on the seafloor. In addition to the filters, 10, 2-L bottles were used to collect whole water for chemical analyses, microbial quantification, and activity assays. Two of these bottles (Ports 9 and 10) were equipped with special tubing to enable collection of samples for DOC analysis, which will be carried out by Dr. Suni Shah Walter (U Delaware, USA). For the other 8 bottles, water was subsampled for inorganic chemistry (Dr. Geoff Wheat, U Alaska, USA), Particulate Organic Carbon (POC), epifluorescent cell quantification of microbes and virus, stable isotope probing experiments, and filtration for molecular biological analyses. A couple of samples were also given to Valeria Naranjo for fungal cultivation. Upon vehicle recovery, the in situ filters were placed in fresh RNALater and frozen. On the ship, stable isotope probing (SIP) experiments were carried out to quantify relative rates of autotrophy and heterotrophy by incubating ~100 mL of either venting fluid or background seawater with ^{13}C -labeled sodium acetate or ^{13}C -labeled sodium bicarbonate. Incubations were run in evacuated serum vials for ~4 days, in duplicate, and sub-sampled via fixing for microscopy and filtration onto combusted GF75 filters for isotope analyses every 12-48 hrs (Table 19). Table 2 shows an example set up for the experiments, including controls. Once on land, cells will be quantified via microscopy and select filters analyzed for isotope enrichment in the POC biomass. 7 sets of experiments (105 vials) were carried out in total during the cruise, 5 in venting fluids and 2 in background seawater.

Samples: In total, we collected 51 SUPR samples on 6 dives, including 33 bottles (66 L) and 18 filters (~120 L filtered on the seafloor) at the sites El Dorado, Tengosed, and La Pulperia (Table 20). This number includes both sites of venting fluids as well as nearby background water, enabling direct comparisons between the microbial community and geochemistry in the venting fluids and the surrounding ocean. Samples will also be compared to animal microbiome

samples collected by the biology team.

Figure 29. Photographs of SUPR sampler mounted on ROV SuBastian.

Top left: SUPR valve, pump, and bottle mounted forward port on ROV. Top right: SUPR bottles and filters in frame on forward starboard of ROV. Bottom left: Typical SUPR intake with temperature probe on ROV porch. Bottom right: Modified SUPR intake for Marker X Tengosed.

Table 19. SUPR Stable isotope probing experiment set up example.

Label	¹³ C Source	Hours
1-A1-TP1	Acetate	12
2-A1-TP2	Acetate	48
3-A1-TP3	Acetate	96
4-A2-TP1	Acetate	12
5-A2-TP2	Acetate	48
6-A2-TP3	Acetate	96
7-B1-TP1	Bicarb	12
8-B1-TP2	Bicarb	48
9-B1-TP3	Bicarb	96
10-B2-TP1	Bicarb	12
11-B2-TP2	Bicarb	48
12-B2-TP3	Bicarb	96
13-C1-TP1	None	12
14-C1-TP2	None	48
15-C1-TP3	None	96

Table 20. SUPR samples.

Dive	Site	date	Sample ID	port	type	sample site
S619	El Dorado	12/4/2023	010	2	bottle	Mkr W vent fluid
S619	El Dorado	12/4/2023	011	3	bottle	Mkr W vent fluid
S619	El Dorado	12/4/2023	012	4	bottle	Mkr W vent fluid
S619	El Dorado	12/4/2023	013	5	bottle	Mkr W vent fluid
S619	El Dorado	12/4/2023	014	9	bottle DOC	Mkr W vent fluid
S619	El Dorado	12/4/2023	015	11	filter, GF75	Mkr W vent fluid
S619	El Dorado	12/5/2023	016	12	filter, PES	Mkr W vent fluid
S619	El Dorado	12/5/2023	020	6	bottle	Mkr W, background seawater
S619	El Dorado	12/5/2023	021	7	bottle	Mkr W, background seawater
S619	El Dorado	12/5/2023	022	10	bottle DOC	Mkr W, background seawater
S619	El Dorado	12/5/2023	023	13	filter, GF75	Mkr W, background seawater
S619	El Dorado	12/5/2023	024	14	filter, PES	Mkr W, background seawater
S619	El Dorado	12/5/2023	blank	8	bottle	blank, no sample taken
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	041	1	bottle	Mrk Q vent fluid
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	042	2	bottle	Mrk Q vent fluid
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	043	3	bottle	Mrk Q vent fluid
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	044	9	bottle DOC	Mrk Q vent fluid
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	045	11	filter, GF75	Mrk Q vent fluid
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	046	12	filter, PES	Mrk Q vent fluid
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	049	7	bottle	Mkr Q, background water
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	051	8	bottle	Mkr Q, background water
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	053	10	bottle DOC	Mkr Q, background water
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	058	13	filter, GF75	Mkr Q, background water
S620	La Pulperia	12/5/2023	059	14	filter, PES	Mkr Q, background water
S621	Tengosed	12/6/2023	071	1	bottle	Mkr X at Tengosed
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	111	2	bottle	Mkr KRW area, background seawater
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	124	3	bottle	Mkr R, background seawater
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	126	6	bottle	Mkr R vent fluids
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	127	7	bottle	Mkr R vent fluids
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	129	10	bottle DOC	Mkr R vent fluids
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	130	4	bottle	Mkr R vent fluids
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	131	11	filter, GF75	Mkr R vent fluids
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	132	12	filter, PES	Mkr R vent fluids
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	133	9	bottle DOC	Mkr R, background seawater

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S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	134	13	filter, GF75	Mkr R, background seawater
S624	El Dorado	12/7/2023	135	14	filter, PES	Mkr R, background seawater
S628	La Pulperia	12/11/2023	219	6	bottle	Mrk Q vent fluid
S628	La Pulperia	12/11/2023	220	7	bottle	Mrk Q vent fluid
S628	La Pulperia	12/11/2023	221	9	bottle DOC	Mrk Q vent fluid
S628	La Pulperia	12/11/2023	222	11	filter, GF75	Mrk Q vent fluid
S628	La Pulperia	12/11/2023	223	12	filter, PES	Mrk Q vent fluid
S628	La Pulperia	12/11/2023	224	10	bottle DOC	right of other samples, still Mkr Q
S628	La Pulperia	12/11/2023	225	8	bottle	Mkr Q, background water
S629	Tengosed	12/12/2023	249	12	filter, PES	background seawater 2031-2020 m
S629	Tengosed	12/12/2023	251	11	filter, GF75	background seawater at 2020m
S629	Tengosed	12/12/2023	252	8	bottle	in Mkr X hole w/ extender
S629	Tengosed	12/12/2023	253	9	bottle DOC	in Mkr X hole w/ extender
S629	Tengosed	12/12/2023	254	10	bottle DOC	in Mkr X hole w/ extender
S629	Tengosed	12/12/2023	255	13	filter, GF75	in Mkr X hole w/ extender
S629	Tengosed	12/12/2023	256	14	filter, PES	in Mkr X hole w/ extender
S629	Tengosed	12/12/2023	257	7	bottle	Mkr X, background seawater at 2020m

Oceanographic observations and Hydrographic/Water sampling

Methods: The main objective of the oceanographic observation program was to characterize the hydrographic and hydrodynamic features in the study area, and to characterize the zooplankton diel vertical migration. This was done through coordinated measurements of the water column using sensors mounted on a ship-deployed CTD Niskin rosette, Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler 300kHz/150kHz/38kHz/ and EK80 wide band echo sounder (38/70/120 kHz), and additional CTD data recorded with sensors mounted on the ROV SuBastian. The CTD-Niskin rosette system is a Sea-Bird Electronics 911plus CTD system carrying 24 twelve-liter Niskin Bottles with two temperature sensors (SBE 4), two conductivity sensors (SBE 3+), two dissolved oxygen sensors (SBE 43), Fluorometer (chlorophyll a)/Turbidity Meter (WetLabs ECO FLNTUD), Transmissometer (WetLabs C-star) and Altimeter. A total of 5 CTD casts were done, named consecutively Fkt231202_CTD_# (Figures 2 and 31-34). CTD data was processed according to the Ocean Best Practices protocol, using the SBE Data Processing software. ADCP were recording and logging during the whole cruise except when conducting bathymetric multibeam mapping. EK80 logging/recording was intermittently turned on at approximately 17:00 GMT-6 and then turned off at ~ 07:00 GMT-6. Absolute geostrophic velocity and Sea Level Anomaly was visualized from AVISO servers to assess daily dynamics. To study water chemistry, particularly for alkalinity, dissolved inorganic carbon and nutrient measurements, twenty eight (28) discrete Niskin bottles samples were collected from the CTD rosettes (n=10) and the ROV (n=18; Table 21).

Preliminary results: During this time of the year, known locally as the transition time, this means that the ITCZ migrates from north to south, causing the shift from rainy season to dry season and the funneling of the northerly winds through the mountain gap in the Lake of Nicaragua. This particular time of the year has been well documented in terms of circulation patterns, as the Costa Rica Thermal Dome genesis is located close to the coast of Costa Rica. Based on the observations of this cruise (Figures 35-37), we observed a strong flow northward during the entire cruise, with evidence of different water masses such as the Tropical Surface Water (TSW), Thirteen degree water mass (13CW), Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) and Lower Circumpolar Water (LCPW). The extent of the Oxygen Minimum Zone (OMZ) was evaluated in relation to the water masses, with a consistent association of the upper oxycline to the 13CW. There was also evidence of ventilation by water mass intrusions that remain to be determined, but we believe this also affected the thickness and depth of the anoxic core of the OMZ, which was shallower and narrower for the first stations and then became wider and deeper, below 500m. Based on altimetry data we determined our study area was under the influence of an cyclonic circulation, that could have influenced the overall water column and the planktonic community distribution observed during ascents.

Table 21. CTD and ROV niskin water samples collected for samples.

Type	Location	Deployment	Bottle/ID	Depth (m)	Purpose
Rosette	HydroMidE	CTD1	1	3164	FON
Rosette	HydroMidE	CTD1	3	2.1	DIC/TA/NUTZ/SUP

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Rosette	HydroMidW	CTD2	1	3140	FON
Rosette	HydroMidW	CTD2	3	2.2	DIC/TA/NUTZ/SUP
Rosette	HydroMidS	CTD3	1	3189	DIC/TA/NUTZ/FON
Rosette	HydroMidS	CTD3	3	2.1	DIC/TA/NUTZ/SUP
Rosette	HydroCenter	CTD4	1	3189	DIC/TA/NUTZ/FON
Rosette	HydroCenter	CTD4	3	1.58	DIC/TA/NUTZ/SUP
Rosette	HydroMidN	CTD5	2	3187	DIC/TA/NUTZ/FON
Rosette	HydroMidN	CTD5	3	1.65	DIC/TA/NUTZ/SUP
ROV	Dorado	619	009	3013	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	La Pulpería	620	036	2840	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Tengosed	621	073	2021	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Tengosed	622	090	1898	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Dorado	624	110	3163	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Dorado	624	144	3016	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Caballito	625	153	3118	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Dorado	626	196	1.5	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Caballito	627	198	3089	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Caballito	627	208	1.5	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	La Pulpería	628	226	2840	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	La Pulpería	628	229	1.5	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Tengosed	629	243	2071	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Tengosed	629	261	1.4	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Dorado	630	276	3064	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Dorado	630	288	33.7	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Fuente	631	298	2722	DIC/TA/NUTZ
ROV	Fuente	631	313	5.37	DIC/TA/NUTZ

Figure 30 - Fkt231202-CTD001

Event/Station	001 (HydroMidE)
File name	Fkt231202_CTD_001
Latitude	8.9465° N
Longitude	87.0407° W
Logger/Operator	Rich Jeong
Start Date (UTC)	06122023
End Date (UTC)	06122023
Start Time (UTC)	06:32
End Time (UTC)	08:43
Start Date (Local)	06122023
End Date (Local)	06122023
Start Time (Local)	00:32
End Time (Local)	02:43
Niskin Bottle	4 bottles fired (1 - 3164m, 2 - 3164 m, 3 - 2.1m, 4 - 2.1m)

Figure 31 - Fkt231202-CTD002

Event/Station	002 (HydroMidW)
File name	Fkt231202_CTD_002
Latitude	9.0202° N
Longitude	87.161° W
Logger/Operator	Rich Jeong
Start Date (UTC)	07122023
End Date (UTC)	07122023
Start Time (UTC)	07:38
End Time (UTC)	09:50
Start Date (Local)	07122023
End Date (Local)	07122023
Start Time (Local)	01:38
End Time (Local)	03:50
Niskin Bottle	4 bottles fired (1 - 3140m, 2 - 3140 m, 3 - 2.2m, 4 - 2.2m)

Figure 32 - Fkt231202-CTD003

Event/Station	003 (HydroMidS)
File name	Fkt231202_CTD_003
Latitude	8.0939°N
Longitude	87.1738°W
Logger/Operator	Rich Jeong
Start Date (UTC)	08122023
End Date (UTC)	08122023
Start Time (UTC)	05:50
End Time (UTC)	07:37
Start Date (Local)	07122023
End Date (Local)	08122023
Start Time (Local)	11:50
End Time (Local)	01:50
Niskin Bottle	4 bottles fired (1 - 3189m, 2 - 3189 m, 3 - 2.2m, 4 - 2.2m)

Figure 33 - Fkt231202-CTD004

Event/Station	004 (HydroCenter)
File name	Fkt231202_CTD_004
Latitude	8.989°N
Longitude	87.1019°W
Logger/Operator	Rich Jeong
Start Date (UTC)	09122023
End Date (UTC)	09122023
Start Time (UTC)	06:55
End Time (UTC)	08:58
Start Date (Local)	09122023
End Date (Local)	09122023
Start Time (Local)	00:55
End Time (Local)	02:58
Niskin Bottle	4 bottles fired (1 - 3181m, 2 - 3181 m, 3 - 1.58m, 4 - 1.58m)

Figure 34 - Fkt231202-CTD005

Event/Station	005 (HydroMidN)
File name	Fkt231202_CTD_005
Latitude	9.093°N
Longitude	87.022°W
Logger/Operator	Rich Jeong
Start Date (UTC)	10122023
End Date (UTC)	10122023
Start Time (UTC)	04:52
End Time (UTC)	06:56
Start Date (Local)	09122023
End Date (Local)	10122023
Start Time (Local)	10:52
End Time (Local)	00:56
Niskin Bottle	4 bottles fired (1 - 3189m, 2 - 3189 m, 3 - 1.65m, 4 - 1.65m)

Figure 35. Summary of current directions from ADCP data.

Figure 36. Summary of sea surface height (altimetry) from AVISO (dates not shown).

Figure 37. Temperature-salinity-oxygen diagram of CTD data.

Outreach

The Fkt230602 outreach program consisted of numerous elements: artists at sea, blogs, livestream and social media engagement, ship-to-shore engagements, video products, press, and ship tours during demobilization.

Artist at Sea

Videographer Diego Gamero of Columbia was the Artist-At-Sea on the Fkt231202 expedition. He conducted interviews and collected shipboard video imagery with the purpose of creating a short documentary film about the goals of the expedition, in Spanish and supplemented with ROV footage. The documentary is available [here](#). Diego also hosted a live ship-to-shore event.

Carlos Hiller – an artist from the June expedition – contributed a lovely drawing of Falkor visiting the deep sea, for use in the guest book, inspired by a concept developed by Marino Protti.

Special Exhibitions

The two artists-at-sea from the June expedition – Michel Droge and Carlos Hiller – continue to use their work to promote the Octopus Odyssey exploration. Both artists had their artwork featured at [SOI's booth at Art Basel](#) during the December expedition. The image below shows the piece that Michel Droge finished after the June expedition that was featured at Art Basel.

Michel Droge presented an interactive exhibition entitled “Beyond Midnight” at the Coram Immersive Media Studio at Bates College November 30 - January 31 as part of the Bates Arts Collaborative. The exhibition shared the experience of the deep sea through collaborative video, sound, and movement, and involved collaboration with video artist Carolina Gonzales Valencia, choreographer Tristan Koepke, and sound artist Asha Tamirisa. Scientists Rachel Lauer and Beth Orcutt joined Michel for a public lecture about the expedition on January 17, 2024. The soundtrack created for the exhibition was also premiered on WMPG 90.9fm Gorham Portland (Maine) that evening. The exhibition was featured in [Bates media](#) and [Bates’ student newspaper](#) and is described on [Michel’s website](#).

The Field Museum created two exhibitions featuring Octopus Odyssey art and science. The “[Changing Face of Science](#)” exhibition opened in February 2024 and showcased Janet Voight’s science. The “[Unseen Oceans](#)” exhibition opened March 15 and featured paintings from Michel Droge and Carlos Hiller and was featured in this TV interview (along with a “fishnado”!): <https://www.fox32chicago.com/video/1426343>

Michel Droge's paintings and drawings inspired from the June expedition were on display at the Sacred Profane brewery in Kennebunk, Maine, for the month of February 2024. Michel and scientist Beth Orcutt presented a public lecture at the brewery on February 15 2024, presented by The New School of Kennebunk.

THE NEW SCHOOL PRESENTS
OCTOPUS ODYSSEY
Showing At Sacred Profane
50 Washington Street
Biddeford, ME

Gallery Opening Thursday, February 15th @ 5PM
Presentations @ 6PM By:

**DR. BETH ORCUTT, VICE PRESIDENT FOR RESEARCH,
BIGELOW LABORATORY FOR OCEAN SCIENCES**
&
**MICHEL DROGE, ARTIST AND VISITING ASSISTANT
PROFESSOR AT BATES COLLEGE**

A Conversation About Deep Sea Science, Octopus Discoveries, Ocean Conservation & Art.

@michel.droge.studio <https://www.micheldroge.com/>

THE NEW SCHOOL **SACRED PROFANE Bates**
Where Students Find Their Voice **Bigelow** | Laboratory for Ocean Sciences

Finally, Michel Droge gave a presentation about their artistic process on Octopus Odyssey as part of an outreach session organized by SOI at the 2024 Ocean Sciences Meeting in New Orleans in late February.

Blogs

The science party contributed four blogs during the course of the expedition for posting on the SOI website. All of these were translated into both English and Spanish to foster cross-cultural understanding and appreciation. In addition, the Artist-at-Sea Diego Gamero and the Berth-of-Opportunity participant Valeria also contributed blogs about their experiences, but these have not yet been published by SOI on their website. Many of these blogs were not posted until well after the expedition due to scheduling challenges for the SOI Communications team.

- Dec 3: [OctoOdyssey \(too\)](#) (Beth Orcutt, Jorge Cortes)
- Dec 4: [Microbial magic in the deep](#) (Julie Huber, Gus Ramirez)
- Jan 6: [Impact of fluid flow and tectonics on life](#) (Marino Protti, Andrew Fisher, Rachel Lauer)
- Jan 6: [Harnessing web tools for research and conservation](#) (Beatriz Naranjo)

Livestream and social media engagement

SOI reported the following engagement statistics for their social media channels as of February 27, 2024:

- Facebook:
 - 1.3M impressions
 - 332k video views
 - 38k engagements
- Twitter:
 - 129k impressions
 - 17k video views
 - 9k engagements
- Instagram:
 - 523k video views
 - 63k engagements
 - reels with over 10k views as of January 20, 2024:
 - [Giant Phantom Jelly](#) (18k views)
 - [Baby octopus being born](#) (23k views)
 - [Gonatus onyx squid carrying babies](#) (32k views)
- YouTube:
 - 17k views of livestream (2nd largest audience in Costa Rica)
 - 22k views of produced videos

Video Products

- The Second Start | Octopus Odyssey (too) - Week 1 (4k views)
- Future Dreams & Ocean Depths | Octopus Odyssey (too) Expedition - Week 2 (593 views)
- [4K Highlights](#) (9.4k views)
- [Science Story - María Isabel Sandoval](#) (504 views)
- [Diego Gamero Artist-At-Sea](#) (131 views)
- Octopus Odyssey (too) | SOI Open House

Ship to Shore Engagements

Eight ship-to-shore engagements happened during the expedition (Table 22), engaging 1,419 people (881 in Costa Rica). Six of these events were in Spanish, one was in English, and an “open house” event was in both languages.

Table 22. Ship-to-Shore engagements during Fkt231202

(total reach 1,419 people; 881 people in Costa Rica)

Date	Group	Audience + Size	Science party involved	Language
4 Dec 2023	University of Costa Rica	Reef Fisheries Undergraduate Class	Valeria Naranjo	Spanish
5 Dec 2023	Lincoln, MA, USA Public School	6th grade students (40)	Randi Rotjan	English

8 Dec 2023	Costa Rica general public	All ages	Valeria Naranjo	Spanish
9 Dec 2023	Sustainable Ocean Alliance Costa Rica + Pelagos	All ages, four coastal communities	Sergio Cambrero, Beatriz Naranjo	Spanish
10 Dec 2023	Youtube Livestream	Film enthusiasts	Diego Gamero	Spanish
11 Dec 2023	INCOPECA	Fisheries resource managers in Costa Rica	Nixon Lara Quesada & Celeste Sacnhez	Spanish
13 Dec 2023	Costa Rica National Academy of Sciences	Scientists in Costa Rica	Oda Breedy, Jorge Cortés, Marino Protti	Spanish
	SOI Open House	General public		Spanish + English

Notable Press (as of February 27 2024)

SOI's [press release](#) and [select image gallery](#) published on January 16, which garnered >410 articles in 22 countries. Notable coverage (according to SOI) includes New Scientist, Scientific American, Atlas Obscura, ABC, CBS, AP News, USA Today, and the Washington Post.

Notable popular press coverage:

- 26 December - Mashable - [Best Deep-Sea Ocean Discovery of 2023](#)
- 9 January - Science Alert - [Astonishing Video Gives Rare Glimpse of Mother Squid's Ultimate Sacrifice](#)
- 16 January - AtlasObscura - [New species of octopus thrives in deep sea nurseries](#)
- 16 January - Gizmodo - [See a newly discovered deep-sea octopus and its adorable alien children](#)
- 16 January - The Independent - [Four new species of deep-sea octopus swim in Costa Rica](#)
- 16 January - NewScientist - [New octopus species discovered by deep-sea submersible](#)
- 16 January - Popular Science - [Four new octopus species discovered in the deep-sea vents off Costa Rica](#)
- 16 January - Scientific American - [Four new octopus species discovered in the deep sea](#)
- 16 January - Saipan Tribune - [Scientists discover 4 new species of deep-sea octopus](#)
- 17 January - IFLscience - [Four new deep-sea octopus species and one "skate park" discovered off Costa Rican coast](#)
- 17 January - ABC 13 News - [4 new species of deep-sea octopus discovered near Costa Rica](#)

- 17 January - Bored Panda - [Scientists discover four new octopus species, and the images are otherworldly](#)
- 17 January - CBS News/Yahoo - [Ocean explorers discover 4 new species of deep-sea octopus, scientists say \(413M viewers\)](#)
- 17 January - Euronews - ["Unique biodiversity": Scientists discover new species of octopus off the coast of Costa Rica.](#)
- 17 January - Globe and Mail - [Scientist discover four new deep-sea octopus species in Costa Rica](#)
- 17 January - MSN - [Researchers discover four new species of octopus \(135M viewers\)](#)
- 18 January - [Delfino.CR](#) -
- 18 January - The Tico Times - [Expedition uncovers four new octopus species](#)
- 18 January - USA Today - [Scientists uncover four new species of octopus in expedition off coast of Costa Rica](#)
- 20 January - Gizmodo - [Deep Sea ROV encounters unknown octopus species](#)
- 21 January - Washington Post - [Researchers discover four new species of octopus](#)
- 1 February - Parley.tv - <https://parley.tv/journal/the-octopus-garden-flourishing-at-the-bottom-of-the-ocean>
- 1 February - crhoy.com - [about Pampa Submarina designation](#)

Ship tours during demobilization

Upon returning to port on 15 December 2023, we conducted one tour for VIPs primarily from the Golfito region.

Just for fun

Fkt231202 Cruise Report

